

Smart AKIS DISSEMINATION PLAN

smart**AKIS**
Smart Farming Thematic Network

Document Summary

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Abstract

Smart AKIS Network Dissemination Plan will guide partners in the dissemination of the Network. The Plan describes the dissemination objectives of the Network, the target groups, key messages and the strategy mix of dissemination tools and activities proposed in order to achieve the expected dissemination goals. The role of partners in the dissemination activities, an indicative work plan and monitoring system of all dissemination activities is also proposed.

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1. Dissemination Strategy

1.1. Dissemination Strategy

The Smart AKIS Dissemination Plan has been designed as a **practical tool for efficiently implementing dissemination activities** in order to support the achievement of the project objectives.

The Smart AKIS Dissemination Plan has been elaborated by INICIATIVAS INNOVADORAS (INI), coordinating Work package 5, in close interaction within the consortium, taking into account regional/national specificities, as well as partners' communication channels and tools, thus supporting the individual partners in maximizing the impact of their dissemination actions while providing the appropriate means to ensure efficient visibility of the activities and outputs of the project as a whole.

In this regard, it should be noted that **all partners will play an active role in the dissemination activities of the project, and that INI will act as a coordinator and facilitator** of the dissemination activities, materials and events planned.

Dissemination of the project will take place at 2 levels, on both of which all partners will get involved:

- **Regional/national level**, in the so-called 7 Innovation Hubs that Smart AKIS will create and promote in France, Germany, Greece, Serbia, Spain, The Netherlands, and UK, where Smart AKIS partners will engage farmers, the industry, research community, advisory services, Operational Groups, on 3 Innovation Workshops to be held at each Hub in 2017 and 2018.
- **EU level**, outreaching the whole of the farmer, research, agricultural equipment and advisory communities, potential end-users and beneficiaries of the Network results and services, embodied and accessible from an EU wide online tool, the Smart Farming Community platform, which will be operational on 2017. INI will play a coordination role on this level, contacting the main projects, programme, networks and initiatives which might act as multiplications in order to engage the EU wide target communities.

The active involvement of stakeholders and target groups is thus, one of the key success factors of the Smart AKIS network; therefore, the Smart AKIS Dissemination Plan proposes the definition of suitable dissemination tools and activities for engaging the target groups in the project. To that end, a **multi-step and multi-channel dissemination strategy** is proposed in order to maximize the impact of the dissemination activities, carefully adjusting the materials and tools to the specific needs, interests and potential for involvement of the target audience. The overall strategy will rely on the following principles, applicable both at the dissemination activities at the Innovation Hubs and at EU level:

- **Localisation of dissemination actions and tools:** Dissemination tools and materials will be translated into the local languages of the national/regional Innovation Hubs and customised in order to better target the regional/national actors' needs, values and profiles. Smart AKIS partners will have a direct say in defining the most effective national/regional dissemination strategies and materials.
- **Representativeness:** The entire value chain of crop production in the national /regional Hubs will be mobilized in order to achieve representativeness of the results, i.e. farmers, extension services,

agricultural consultants, industry (SMEs, multinationals and national associations), government and the general public. Partners will identify and assess regional/national stakeholders in order to fully identify and point out those key stakeholders that will be necessary to involve on the activities in order to be successful.

- **Identification and leverage of networks** (associations, unions, clusters, technology platforms, etc), are addressed as “meta-targets” or “multipliers” for achieving a multiplier effect of the dissemination activities in the national/regional Innovation Hubs, and most of all at the EU level.
- **Identification and active engagement of innovators and early adopters:** a pro-active approach towards innovators and early adopters will be taken, by pinpointing and involving them early in the Network in order for them to act as ambassadors for the promotion of the project among their neighbours and colleagues, thus multiplying the impact of the dissemination activities in the national/regional Innovation Hubs.

The Dissemination Plan is divided into 4 main sections and 6 Annexes.

In the **first introductory chapter** the overall strategy is described: dissemination principles and goals, analysis of target groups is made considering their expectations and needs, main messages to convey in the dissemination activities, the products and deliverables that will be the subject of the dissemination activities and finally the strategy mix of dissemination tools and activities, are introduced.

A **second chapter** describes the dissemination tools put in place by the Network: visual identity, publicity materials, webportal and social media strategy and digital newsletters.

A **third chapter** is devoted to the dissemination activities planned, including network and non-network events, the delivery of press releases and publications and the outreach of key target groups through networking activities and person to person meetings.

The implementation of the strategy and plan is addressed on a **fourth and last chapter**, where the governance system put in place in order to ensure an effective coordination of all dissemination efforts and the planning and monitoring systems of the Dissemination Plan are described.

The Plan is completed by 6 annexes:

- Visual Identity Handbook.
- Webportal architecture.
- Dissemination Work Plan template.
- Partners Dissemination Report template.
- Network Dissemination Report template.
- Dissemination Balanced Scorecard.

1.2. Smart AKIS Objectives

The main objective of Smart-AKIS is to set up a self-sustainable Thematic Network on Smart Farming Technology designed for the effective exchange between research, industry, extension and the farming community so that direct applicable research and commercial solutions are widely disseminated and grassroots level needs and innovative ideas thoroughly captured, thus contributing to close the research and innovation divide in this area

Smart AKIS is incepted as Thematic Network in Smart Farming with the following specific objectives:

Objective 1: Create an inventory of direct applicable solutions from the large stock of research results and commercial applications.

Smart-AKIS will create an inventory of research results and industrial applications in the area of Smart Farming Technology by systematically reviewing European and national research projects in the areas of precision farming, farm management information systems and agricultural automation and robotics. A wide range of solutions will be included, spanning from solutions that are still in the experimental/piloting stage and that could benefit from users' feedback, all the way to solutions that have been adopted in practice but are not widespread. The Smart Farming Technology solutions will be evaluated on the basis of criteria such as potential to increase yield and/or quality, decrease production costs and reduce environmental impact. Efficient searching in the inventory will be possible as Smart-AKIS will draw on the results of VALERIE (EU project coordinated by P2 DLO), which is developing a semantic search engine for the agricultural domain for valorisation of research results.

Objective 2: Assess end-user needs and interests, and identify factors influencing adoption taking into account regional/national specificities.

Smart-AKIS will assess end-users needs and interests and will identify and characterise the factors that influence generation, adoption and diffusion of Smart Farming Technology innovations. The project will also identify best practices in the use of Smart Farming Technology and will explore and assess the processes at play and the barriers for the adoption and mainstreaming of these innovations in the different regional/national contexts. Emphasis will be placed on social factors such as the needs, beliefs and attitudes of farmers and other actors. The outcomes and methodologies of PRO-AKIS and SOLINSA will be used to support the appraisal of innovation processes specific to Smart Farming Technology and the role of advisory services in adoption and generation of innovations.

Objective 3: Generate multi-actor, innovation-based collaborations among different stakeholders.

Smart-AKIS will facilitate the development of interactive innovation processes in the national/regional agricultural value chains, by bringing together farmers, advisors, researchers, industrial partners and other actors in interactive innovation workshops. A conceptual framework will be implemented (see Section 1.3), by which the Smart Farming Technology solutions inventoried (WP1) will be adapted to the regional/national contexts (WP2) for an effective and targeted dissemination. Grassroots-level ideas will be captured and channelled using the same approach, resulting in concrete innovation-based projects developed in response to practical needs of end-users, which will be more quickly put into practice thanks to the empowerment of the actors and the co-ownership generated during the collaborations. This process will be widened to the EU level for generating cross-border collaborations in the area of Smart Farming Technology.

Objective 4: Set up of an ICT tool for the on-line assessment of the Smart Farming Technology solutions and the crowdsourcing of grassroots-level ideas and needs.

Smart-AKIS will implement an online and interactive approach to communication, interaction and knowledge sharing and exchange through the use of a specially designed ICT tool, the “Smart Farming Community Platform”, which will deploy the collected information and knowledge on Smart Farming Technology in the form of easily accessible end-user material following the EIP-Service Point format. The Smart Farming Community Platform will be the tool for online assessment of the Smart Farming Technology solutions by stakeholders across Europe and will allow for the crowdsourcing of grassroots-level ideas and needs for research. Smart-AKIS will add Smart Farming Technology specific information to VALERIE’s search engine and knowledge base, expanding its ontology with specific concepts. Upon project finalisation, the Smart Farming Community Platform will be integrated onto the EIP-Service Point ensuring the long term accessibility of material produced.

Objective 5: Liaise with EIP-AGRI and its structures.

Smart-AKIS will establish direct communication with the European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) and its structures (Focus Groups, Service Point, Operational Groups (OG) and national clusters) in order to maximize stakeholder mobilization and enhance the impact of the project activities and outcomes for closing the research and innovation divide in the area of Smart Farming Technology. Smart-AKIS will serve many future OGs as it lies across the whole agricultural sector and can support a large number of applications (i.e. tilling, seeding, transplanting, fertilizing, irrigation, crop protection, harvesting, etc.). The project will include in its activities the newly created Operational Groups on a thematic and geographic basis. Smart-AKIS will also establish links with the other EIP-AGRI Thematic Networks (TN).

1.3. Dissemination Objectives

As a Thematic Network, dissemination of Smart AKIS is at the core of the proposed strategy of the Network. Thus, the following dissemination objectives are agreed:

- **AWARENESS RAISING:** The economic and environment benefits of adopting Smart Farming Technologies will be the at the core of the dissemination of Smart AKIS activities, targeting both the farmer community, end-users of such technologies, facing different obstacle and hurdles for their adopting, as well as society at large, which is becoming a mature and sophisticated market accessing and demanding more and more information on agriculture and food production processes, and is becoming more and more aware about the impact that smart technologies in the so called digital transformation of the economy. To that end, testimonials of end-users on the benefits reaped following the adoption of such technologies and the access to an interactive inventory of smart farming technologies in the so called Smart Farming Community Platform will be extensively disseminated through the Network communication channels.
- **PROMOTION:** The Network will actively promote the ecosystem of EU and national projects and initiatives where Smart AKIS operates, providing information and referring interested end-users to relevant sources of information on relation to the Smart AKIS Network goals, its links to other Thematic Networks, EIP-AGRI, national and transitional Operational Groups, other EU projects linked to smart farming, agriculture knowledge and innovation systems (AKIS), Agriculture, digital single market, open research policies, etc. To that end, the Network will act as a multiplier of

all relevant information and events linked to such complementary initiatives, and will set up close communication channels with such projects and initiatives. The backing of the EU through synergistic funds and programmes to such initiatives (Horizon 2020, EARD, ERDF, financial instruments by EIB) will also be highlighted, as well as the role of Women in Science and Agriculture by the use of non-stereotyped images and the promotion of testimonials and images featuring women farmers, researchers, IT providers, etc.

- **PARTICIPATION:** As a Thematic Network, Smart AKIS relies on the involvement and participation of target groups, both at the national/regional level of the 7 Innovation Hubs' activities as well as at a European level, through the Smart Farming Community Platform. Engagement of target groups is key for the selection of the most promising smart farming solutions to be demonstrated at each Innovation Hub, as well as for the generation of new collaborative projects for the joint development or transfer of smart farming solutions, leading to multifactor innovation projects or Operational Groups.
- **DISSEMINATION:** Dissemination of Network progress, deliverables, events, factsheets and services following a transparency and accountability spirit will take all along the project implementation, through a variety of dissemination activities, mainly related to the webportal and the social media profiles of the Network, reinforced by the role played by multipliers, specifically the EIP-AGRI Service Point.
- **EXPLOITATION:** Smart AKIS has got a very results oriented approach as a Network, as it aims at increasing the adoption rate of smart farming technologies by European farmers. Thus, main outputs and deliverables of the project have been defined taking into consideration its widest use by regional/national Innovation Hubs target groups and at the EU level. To that end, the strategy of the Network is to make the main 2 results of the project, accessible as a service through an open on line tool, the so called Smart Farming Community Platform, where target groups from all Europe will be able to 1) access, use, assess and propose the most promising smart farming technologies and research results, taking into consideration the farmers' needs, in a searchable database of smart farming solutions, and 2) to network and cooperate with other farmers, researchers, providers, in the definition of multiactor innovation projects and/or operational groups on smart farming.
- **NETWORKING:** As a Network, Smart AKIS will coordinate and liaise with other relevant regional and EU network and stakeholders at the policy level already involved on the policy areas addressed (Agriculture, Research & Innovation, Digital Market, etc), contributing thus to the further debate and scientific evidence allowing to push up smart farming, precision agriculture and agriculture technology into the current policy agenda. To that end, Smart AKIS will seek the coordination with EIP-AGRI, DG Agriculture & Rural Development, DG Research & Innovation, DG Regional & Urban Policy, as well as with main representatives from target groups, such as CEMA, European Landowners and Farmers Associations, agriculture research centers, advisory services, agriculture engineering associations, as well as with the other Thematic Networks. Specifically, Smart AKIS will provide further insights into the Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR) and EIP-AGRI.

Following these dissemination objectives, the following targets are agreed:

Objective	Result Indicators
Awareness raising & promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1.000 visitors at webportal a month • 2.000 pages visited at webportal a month • 1.000 Twitter followers • 500 Facebook Likes to page • 3.000 people outreached by digital newsletter. • 2.500 people outreached by promotional materials.
Participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 700 participants in 7 regional Innovation Workshops • 60 participants at 1 transnational Innovation Workshop
Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 60 participants at Final Conference • 50 events where Network is actively disseminated • 1.250 participants in events where Network is actively disseminated
Exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 700 stakeholders from Innovation Hubs registered on the Platform • 2.500 stakeholders from other EU countries registered on the Platform • 2.000 monthly visits to Smart Farming Community Platform
Networking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100 policy makers reached with recommendations and policy briefs • 8 Thematic Networks coordinated with • 50 Operational Groups and national EIP clusters coordinated with

Table 1. Dissemination Results Indicators

1.4. Target Groups

Smart AKIS Network addresses 4 primary Target Groups:

- **FARMERS:** Including farmers' associations and federations, farmers' unions, farmers' cooperatives, agricultural chambers, etc. This is the first and foremost target group of Smart AKIS, as final aim is to increase the adoption level of smart farming technologies by this group.
- **INDUSTRY:** The Smart Farming industry comprises a wide array of multinational companies, SMEs, star-ups in different fields: precision agriculture machinery, sensors, software (FMIS, DSS), IT tools, remote sensing, agri-food industry, etc, even if close to their clients' needs, there are still gaps and needs perceived by farmers which are not responded by current equipment and solutions. Interaction and collaboration between industry, research and end-users is necessary to bring more marketable solutions for smart farming.
- **RESEARCH:** Universities, Research & Technology Organisations and corporate researchers in the fields of precision agriculture, sensing, IT systems, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) and drones, earth observations systems, do showcase very promising research results in related fields of smart farming, but fail to transfer such results into marketable products and solutions due to its lack of contact with potential end-users and the industry.
- **INNOVATION BROKERS:** Under this group, we might find any kind of intermediary body or facilitator, allowing to match and bridge the gap between research, innovation and practitioners (farmers) for the adoption, transfer or development of new smart farming solutions. Following the EIP-AGRI definition, Innovation Brokers act as a go-between and connects innovation actors

(farmers, researchers, NGOs, etc.) around an idea that may become an innovation. Brokers help to find and refine innovative ideas, find the adequate partners and funding. As such, we find any kind of advisory and extension services and authorities, governmental/public and private advisory services, and agricultural consultants, etc.

Following the Operational Groups strategy and approach promoted by EIP-AGRI, the primary target groups of Smart AKIS Network mirror the three main actors involved on multi-actor projects (farmer, industry and research) plus the new role played by Innovation Brokers, whatever their nature.

Besides, Smart AKIS Network also addresses 2 secondary Target Groups:

- **AUTHORITIES & POLICY-MAKERS:** representatives of agricultural authorities (ministries, departments) related to Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), EARDF Regional Development Programmes, experts on regulatory issues related to the use of smart technologies in agriculture, fertilization, ground water and air pollution, UAVs; standardization and certification bodies, EU's DG RESEARCH, DG AGRI, DG INDUSTRY, DG ENV, SCAR, Public Environmental Monitoring Authorities, organizations in sustainable agriculture, organic farming, food consumers associations, etc. there's a bested interest on the further regulation, promotion and endorsement of smart farming as a solution for the competitiveness, resource efficiency and environmental challenges of future farming where such authorities can play a key role, both as recipients of learning, best cases and recommendations drawn from Smart AKIS Network as well as multiplier agents of dissemination efforts.
- **RESEARCH & INNOVATION NETWORKS:** All kind of Research & Innovation network, project and initiative in relation to smart farming technologies is considered as a secondary target group, both in terms of their potential agency on the promotion, dissemination and endorsement of the Network results, as in terms of capturing potential insights, knowledge and solutions potentially subject of dissemination by the Network. Amongst them, EIP-AGRI and other TNs; research networks and initiatives on precision agriculture, sustainable agriculture, agricultural machinery, information technology in agriculture, Earth observation; Relevant European Technology Platforms (those in the areas of Bio-based Economy, Environment and ICT), the Agriculture Food Security and Climate Change and Water JPIs and other networks and initiatives at EU level.

Smart AKIS Network Target Groups can also be classified attending to their geographical scope, as referred target Groups can operate at a micro, meso and macro level:

- **Micro-level:** Target Groups located at a local level, main pertaining to the primary Target Groups, well-known and accessible by all partners inside partners' organisations; local communities; local authorities; other projects at local level, etc.
- **Meso-level:** Primary and secondary Target Groups, at regional and national level, including main public authorities with competencies in agriculture, R&I, certification and so on. Some partners are included under this category such as ACTA in France.
- **Macro-level:** Located at EU and international level, both primary target groups, represented by some partners such as CEMA (industry) or EurAgEng (Innovation Brokers) and other EU wide associations and networks such as Landowners' Association or Young Farmer Association, as well as secondary target groups such as EIP-AGRI, other Thematic Networks, EU DGs, etc.

In order to maximise the impact of Smart AKIS Network dissemination activities, all partners have conducted a mapping exercise leading to the identification of target groups on each of the described categories, at local, regional, national and EU level. Resulting list of identified Target Groups allows partners to have access to a database of their key target groups, ensuring their engagement in Network dissemination efforts. Partners have all in all identified more than 100 organisations that will be engaged and take part on Smart AKIS dissemination efforts.

In parallel to the Target Groups mapping, partners have conducted an assessment of Target Groups, in order to identify:

- Interests and expectation on the Network.
- Project outputs of their interest.
- Potential contribution & problems to be addressed for their engagement.
- Dissemination strategies to engage them in Smart-AKIS Network.

This assessment has allowed understanding the different Target Groups needs and expectations, leading to the definition of specific messages to their needs, the characterisation of Network outputs tailored to their expectations, as well as the design of the dissemination strategy of these groups in terms of tools and activities to address. All of these blocks are described in the following sections of the Dissemination Plan.

As a result of the assessment, the following findings can be highlighted:

Target Group	Expectations	Smart AKIS services of interest	Engagement strategies
Farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get a better overview on suitable smart farming technologies used in Europe for their crops, lands, climatic area, etc, specifically in terms of the potential solution of environmental problems, increase in efficiency and productivity and return on investment of smart farming technologies. • Improve access to technology providers on smart farming. • Stronger voice towards policy-makers reinforcing their needs on policy requests: investment support, skills upgrade, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to information on a simple and practical way on <u>what Smart Farming is</u>, and on how farmers can benefit from the adoption of already available solutions. • Access to <u>Inventory of Smart Farming solutions</u>, allowing searching, selecting and assessing available Smart Farming solutions based upon farmers' needs. • Possibility to get to know and disseminate in turn, how the adoption of smart solutions has increased the performance of farmers, all over Europe. • Participation on <u>Innovation Workshops</u> where Smart Farming solutions will be demonstrated and farmers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking & personal meetings by partners. • Dissemination of Network in the framework of partner' events and other agriculture related events, conferences, fairs and field days. • Information about Network's Smart Community Platform and webportal through partners' and multipliers' channels and specialised mass media. • Invitation to take part on Innovation Workshops and Smart AKIS Conference.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closer links to industry and research bringing up front their needs for the supply of suitable smart farming technologies. 	<p>will be able to propose new uses for such solutions, as well as present end-users needs that might be solved by smart technologies.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement into a <u>Networking community</u> where contacts and cooperation will be facilitated with other farmers, researchers, advisors and agricultural equipment companies in the framework of innovation projects for the transfer or the development of new smart solutions tailored to your real needs and interests. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invitation to subscribe to digital newsletter, Inventory of Smart Farming Solutions and Networking Area.
<p>Industry</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote benefits of smart farming technologies and services with a focus on EU farmers' needs. • Increase visibility on solutions developed and made available by the industry. • Support the role the agriculture machinery industry performs in agriculture at EU level. • Learn about technology acceptance & use at EU level in order to promote its adoption. • Possibilities for absorbing innovation-driven research coming up from academia. • Verification of solutions during the development phase from end-users. • Inspiration for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to information on the real needs faced by farmers in Europe allowing coming up with innovative solutions and new approaches for new products and services. • Access to Inventory of Smart Farming solutions for showcasing and advertising available technologies and solutions to a wide number of farmers all over Europe. • Participation on Innovation Workshops where commercial solutions will be demonstrated where farmers will help identifying new uses for such solutions. • Engagement into a <u>Networking community</u> where contacts and cooperation will be facilitated with farmers, researchers, advisors and other agricultural equipment companies for the promotion of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking & personal meetings by partners. • Dissemination of Network in the framework of partner's events and other agriculture related events, conferences, fairs and field days. • Information about Network's Smart Community Platform and webportal through partners' and multipliers' channels and specialised mass media. • Invitation to take part on Innovation Workshops and Smart AKIS Conference. • Invitation to subscribe to digital newsletter, Inventory of Smart Farming Solutions and Networking Area.

	development of new solutions based on cooperation with end-users.	innovation projects for the transfer or the development of new smart solutions tailored to farmers' real needs and interests.	
Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transfer of research based results into marketable products. • Adapt basic and applied research agenda fitting farmer's needs. • Access to smart farming industry and farmer community to get engaged into relevant and needs based new R&I projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to relevant information on the real needs faced by farmers in Europe allowing coming up with innovative solutions and new approaches based upon research based knowledge and technologies. • Access to Inventory of Smart Farming solutions for showcasing and advertising research based technologies and solutions to a wide number of farmers all over Europe. • Participation on Innovation Workshops where research results based smart farming solutions will be demonstrated where farmers will help identifying new uses for such solutions. • Engagement into a Networking community where contacts and cooperation will be facilitated with farmers, other researchers, advisors and agricultural equipment companies for the promotion of innovation projects or Operational Groups for the transfer or the development of new smart solutions tailored to farmers' real needs and interests. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking & personal meetings by partners. • Dissemination of Network in the framework of partner's events and other agriculture related events, conferences, fairs and field days. • Information about Network's Smart Community Platform and webportal through partners' and multipliers' channels and specialised scientific mass media. • Invitation to take part on Innovation Workshops and Smart AKIS Conference. • Invitation to subscribe to digital newsletter, Inventory of Smart Farming Solutions and Networking Area.
Innovation Brokers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve access to technology providers on smart farming and to available commercial 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to information on the latest trends on Smart Farming. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking & personal meetings by partners. • Dissemination of Network

	<p>solutions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of a better service to farmers, by the delivery of guidance on the smart farming solutions most useful, as well as on the most effective methods for engaging them for the transfer and adoption of such solutions • Better access to industry and research for their involvement on new collaborative innovation projects tacking end-users needs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidance on how to better disseminate and demonstrate the economic and environmental benefits of Smart Farming to farmers, allowing disseminating best practices and experiences among advisors and Innovation Brokers from all over Europe. • Access to Inventory of Smart Farming solutions allowing for searching, selecting and assessing available Smart Farming technologies based upon farmers’ needs in order to provide a better advisory service. • Participation on Innovation Workshops where Smart Farming solutions will be demonstrated and brokers will be able to propose new uses for such solutions, as well as present the needs faced by farmers that might be solved by smart technologies. • Engagement into a Networking community where contacts and cooperation will be facilitated with farmers, researchers, other advisors and agricultural equipment companies for the promotion of innovation projects or Operational Groups for the transfer or the development of new smart solutions tailored to farmers’ real needs and interests. 	<p>in the framework of partner’s events and other agriculture related events, conferences, fairs and field days.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information about Network’s Smart Community Platform and webportal through partners’ and multipliers’ channels and specialised scientific mass media. • Invitation to take part on Innovation Workshops and Smart AKIS Conference. • Invitation to subscribe to digital newsletter, Inventory of Smart Farming Solutions and Networking Area.
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<p>Authorities & Policy makers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information on the economic and environmental impact following the adoption of smart farming technologies, in order to mainstream the support to such technologies into regulation and support measures. • Information on barriers hindering smart farming solutions in Europe. • Information on best practices and support services further allowing embracing smart farming solutions (advisory services, financial services, etc) for the definition of new tools. • Links and contact with smart farming solutions and agricultural machinery industry for tackling further support measures. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to relevant information on the real needs faced by farmers in Europe for the adoption of smart farming solutions. • Access to the EU academia and industry communities providing smart farming solutions. • National and EU wide recommendations for the delivery of further support measures allowing adopting smart farming technologies in Europe. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking & personal meetings by partners. • Dissemination of Network in the framework of partner's events and other agriculture related events, conferences, fairs and field days. • Information about Network's Smart Community Platform and webportal through partners' and multipliers' channels. • Invitation to take part on Innovation Workshops and Smart AKIS Conference. • Invitation to subscribe to digital newsletter, Inventory of Smart Farming Solutions and Networking Area.
<p>R&I Networks</p>	<p>EIP-AGRI: Access to best practices in smart farming economic and environmental benefits, best practice on smart farming support measures, and access to updated smart farming solutions and technologies.</p> <p>Operational Groups and national EIP Clusters: access to grass roots innovation driven ideas coming up from farmer community and access to a forum where to promote multi-actor innovation initiatives.</p> <p>Links between Thematic Networks for the delivery of</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to relevant information on the real needs faced by farmers in Europe for the adoption of smart farming solutions, allowing starting new R&I projects, networks and drawing tailored recommendations. • Access to the EU academia and industry communities providing smart farming solutions. • National and EU wide recommendations for the delivery of further support measures allowing adopting smart farming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking & personal meetings by partners. • Dissemination of Network in the framework of partner's events and other agriculture related events, conferences, fairs and field days. • Information about Network's Smart Community Platform and webportal through partners' and multipliers' channels. • Invitation to take part on Innovation Workshops and Smart AKIS

	<p>common policy recommendations aimed at current and new Focus Groups and aimed at national policy makers.</p>	<p>technologies in Europe.</p>	<p>Conference.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invitation to subscribe to digital newsletter, Inventory of Smart Farming Solutions and Networking Area.
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Table 2. Target Groups Analysis

1.5. Key messages

Key messages for primary target groups are the following:

Target Group	Key messages
Farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get to know real cases on how Smart Farming can increase the profitability of your farm and help you comply with the demanding European environmental legislation. • Don't get overwhelmed about the tech hot topics of the day like drones, agricultural big data, precision agriculture, etc, there is a wide pool of already available and easy to understand smart farming solutions that can help you increase your productivity. • Get involved and provide feedback, so that research and industry will produce solutions tailored to your needs and interests.
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You can increase your sales by showcasing and advertising your commercial offer outreaching a wide number of potential end-users, the EU farmer community. • Test and validate your new smart farming products and services with communities of end-users all along Europe. • Grasp new business opportunities for the delivery of new products and services by being aware of farmers' needs and the most promising research based technology results. • Bring up in the EU agenda the needs for the further support of measures, tools and policies facilitating the adoption of smart farming.
Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-creation is the name of the game. If you want results-oriented research that has a positive impact on productivity and environmental sustainability you have to collaborate with industry and end-users. • Don't let your promising inventions, patents and solutions lay to waste: test and get feedback on the real demand for such technology or solutions both from the

	<p>farmer and industry communities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Want to know the real needs of farmers and the latest trends in the industry? Get updated information on the state of play on the smart farming field and trigger new results oriented research initiatives.
<p>Innovation Brokers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> You are aware of the benefits of Smart Farming but gave difficulties on getting updated on the latest technologies and solutions and those most relevant to your farmers. Get updated information on the latest solutions supply. Get to know best practices and case studies of agricultural services successfully transferring smart farming solutions to farmers’ communities overcoming the traditional barriers faced in such endeavours. Get involved on regional innovation ecosystems with farmers, other agricultural advisor, research and industry where you will be able to come up with new smart farming transfer and development projects.

Table 3. Smart AKIS Key messages

1.6. Outputs assessment

Smart AKIS Network and project will produce a number of outputs and deliverables, that will be of the interest of target groups, and which will be the subject of specific strategies for their dissemination and adoption.

The following table summarises Network’s main outputs, the target group they are aimed at and the dissemination strategies to be followed so their contents are widely disseminated to target groups:

Outputs	Target Group	Dissemination Strategy
<p>Research Results and Industry Solutions in Smart Farming: database and report. WP1.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmers Innovation Brokers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The database will be available in the Inventory of Smart Farming Solutions at the Smart Community platform, as a searchable and updatable tool. Inventory of Smart Farming Solutions extensively disseminated through: Network webportal; digital newsletter; popular articles in specialised mass media; Innovation Workshops; and the participation at other events.
<p>Report on farmers’ needs, innovative ideas and interests. WP2.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmers Innovation Brokers Research Industry Authorities & policy makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deliverable available at webportal. Main results will be the subject of the contents of pieces of news, digital newsletter and popular articles. Regional and common needs and interest to be

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R&I Networks. 	presented in regional Innovation Workshops.
Report on factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion processes. WP2.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers • Innovation Brokers • Industry • Authorities & policy makers • R&I Networks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable available at webportal. • Main results will be the subject of the contents of pieces of news, digital newsletter and popular articles. • Regional and common needs and interests to be presented in regional Innovation Workshops.
Policy Recommendations on Smart Farming. WP3.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers • Innovation Brokers • Research • Industry • Authorities & policy makers • R&I Networks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable available at webportal. • Main results will be the subject of the contents of pieces of news, digital newsletter and popular articles. • Main results presented in Smart AKIS Conference, other events and at personal meetings with key stakeholders at national and EU level including EIP-AGRI and other Thematic Networks.
7 Policy Briefs. WP3.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authorities & policy makers • R&I Networks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable available at webportal. • Main results will be the subject of the contents of pieces of news, digital newsletter and popular articles. • Main results presented in Smart AKIS Conference, other events and at personal meetings with key stakeholders at regional and national level
Smart Community Platform with 1) SFT solutions, 2) networking facility, 3) virtual test bed and 4) webportal. WP4.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers • Innovation Brokers • Research • Industry • Authorities & policy makers • R&I Networks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart Community platform services accessible from Smart AKIS webportal, main entry point to the platform. • Extensive dissemination of the platform services through all communication tools and at all activities.

Table 4. Smart AKIS Output assessment

1.7. Dissemination strategy mix

The combined assessment of the Stakeholders Analysis, Key Messages and main dissemination worthy outputs or deliverables, has allowed defining a dissemination strategy mix, composed of a combination of Dissemination Tools and Activities, described in sections 2 and 3 that will allow successfully engaging the target groups and achieve planned Results Indicators:

As a result of this assessment a matrix or combination of dissemination tools and activities are planned, described in following sections.

Target Groups	Dissemination tools	Dissemination activities
Farmers Industry Research Innovation Brokers Authorities & policymakers R&I Networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logo and visual identity • Webportal • Digital newsletter • Social media • Publicity materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network events • Non-network events • Scientific and popular publications • Press relations • Networking & personal meetings

Table 5. Smart AKIS Dissemination strategy mix

2. Dissemination tools

2.1. Visual identity

The logo of Smart AKIS (font, colors, etc) and its use on different documents is described in Annex 5.1.

Figure 1. Smart AKIS logo

The logo chosen (Figure 1) is clear, captures the attention of the target groups and communicates the main concepts of Smart AKIS:

- A leaf referring to the agriculture background of the network.
- Green and orange colours linking the logo to EIP-AGRI visual identity colours.
- A grid or mesh inspiring a network made up of different coloured dots, reflecting the multi-actor approach of the Network.

Furthermore, in order to communicate a coherent message towards the target groups, as the Smart AKIS name is not self-explanatory on its nature, the logo is accompanied by a definition “Smart Farming Thematic Network” and by a banner image that will be consistently used on the different materials, showcasing an agricultural landscape and a drone, encompassing thus the smart farming subject of the Network.

Figure 2: Smart AKIS banner

These elements create a consistent image order to ensure that the target groups easily recall the Network and its orientation. All partners are expected to apply the logo in the dissemination activities and respective publications to facilitate recognition of Smart AKIS Network and thus increase its impact.

In particular, all dissemination material will showcase the Smart AKIS logo, the EU emblem, and a clear statement that the project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, through the following text: This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 696294.

The use of the logo is described in Annex 5.1, where the Visual identity Handbook also includes the flowing templates to be consistently used by all partners:

Deliverables template

Figure 3. Deliverable template.

Power Point template

Figure 4. Power Point template

Letter template

Figure 5. Letter template.

Digital firm for Digital Newsletter

Figure 6. Digital firm template.

2.2. Webportal

Smart AKIS webportal (www.smart-akis.com) will be the main communication and dissemination channel of the Network. It showcases the following characteristics:

- Webportal as main entry point for main public deliverables of the project, as well as to the services put in place by the Network for its target groups: 1) Inventory of Smart Farming Technologies (resulting from Work Package 1) and Networking area with a pool of grassroots project ideas (resulting from Work Package 3) and a matching engine allowing the generation of multi-actor innovation projects in Smart Farming.
- Information provided on Smart AKIS Network partnership, mission, goals, as well as on Smart Farming.

- Smart Farming benefits, as well as Smart AKIS deliverables and services showcased following the different target groups' expectations, redirecting them to the most suitable webportal sections.
- Information provided on EIP-AGRI and other thematic Networks, embedding the network within the overall EU agro-innovation ecosystem.
- Links with EIP-AGRI, other Thematic Networks and partners' webportals, looking for a better positioning and traffic of visitors. Relevant news on activities by partners related to Smart Farming to be disseminated through the Network webportal.
- Multi-lingual web-portal: English version of the webportal will be regularly updated with news and events feed. Static versions of the webportal available in French, Dutch, German, Greek, Spanish and Serbian.
- Access to the Network social media profiles in Facebook, Twitter and Youtube.

The architecture of the designed webportal, fully described in Annex 5.2 is the following:

HOME: Homepage with access to full navigation bar, different language version and social media.

NETWORK:

- Smart AKIS: Description of Network goals and results.
- What is Smart Farming?: Overall description of Smart Farming and of the three specific fields addressed by the Network: 1) farm management information systems, 2) precision agriculture and 3) automation and robotics.
- EIP-AGRI and Thematic Networks: Description and link to EIP-AGRI; description of what are Thematic Networks and links to existing Networks; description of what are Operational Groups and the role of Innovation Brokers.
- Partners: Information on Smart AKIS consortium partners.
- Innovation Hubs: Map with the location of the 7 innovation hubs created in Smart-AKIS, including information on existing Operational Groups and funding calls. Information provided on the role of innovation hubs on the project, mainly on WP2 and WP3, and how stakeholders can participate and benefit. Information provided on the main Contact Point details for each innovation hub.
- Results: Access to public Deliverables of interest for target groups, once available.

NEWS

- News: News from the project, partners and smart farming.
- Events: three categories of events will be advertised: Network and partners' events, EIP-AGRI related events and smart farming events organised by other initiatives.
- Newsletter: registration form to voluntarily receive the Network newsletter.

SMART FARMING PLATFORM

- Inventory of Smart Farming solutions: Access to the solutions database.
- Networking area: Access to multiactor networking area.

MEDIA

- Press releases: repository of network press releases.
- Brochure: Downloadable version of Network brochures.
- Project Brief: Power point presentation PDF-ed with Network info.
- Recommendations: Policy and Recommendations Brief: Once deliverables of WP3 are available.

- Images: Gallery of copyright free pictures by Network and partners.

I AM A:

Benefits and services of the Network for the 4 primary target groups are described, specifically pointing out through links the services provided by the Smart Farming Community Platform.

- Farmer
- Innovation Broker.
- Researcher.
- Provider of Smart Farming solutions.

Figure 7. Smart AKIS webportal homepage.

The webportal is managed by INICIATIVAS INNOVADORAS by WordPress who will feed regularly the News & Events section with the collaboration of appointed Communication Officers from partners.

Google Analytics will allow the ongoing monitoring of the number of visitors and the traffic on the webportal sections, and such intelligent information will be used for improving the impact of the webportal.

Partners’ webportals will also echo Smart AKIS Network news and events, positively impacting on the traffic of the webportal. To that end, partners’ webportals showcase a relevant outreach on their areas of influence:

Partner	Webportal	Monthly visits
AUA	www.aua.gr/	190.000
ACTA	www.acta.asso.fr/	8.865
	www.vignevin.com/	9.603
	www.arvalisinstitutduvegetal.fr/index.html	10.000
	www.arvalis-infos.fr/index.html	120.000
	www.yvoir.fr	30.000

BioSense	www.biosens.rs/index.php/en	580
CEMA	www.cema-agri.org	15.400
CUMA	www.ouest.cuma.fr/content/federation-regionale-des-cuma-de-louest	
David Tinker & Associates / EurAgEng	www.eurageng.eu	2.500
Delphy	www.delphy.nl	1.400
DLG	www.dlg.org	1.200
DLO	www.wur.nl/	750.000
Iniciativas Innovadoras	www.iniciativas-innovadoras.es	630
INTIA	www.intiasa.es	7.500
ZALF	www.zalf.de	30.000

Table 6. Smart AKIS partners websites

2.3. Digital Newsletter.

The distribution of 3 digital newsletters is planned all along the project. Subscription to the newsletter will be voluntary via the webportal. Mail chimp software will be used for the management and distribution of the digital newsletters, ensuring the accurate monitoring of the impact of the newsletters.

Newsletter will act as a compilation of news, events and information published on website that will be distributed to voluntary subscribers. Newsletters' content will be based upon posts by INICVIATIVAS INNOVADORAS in webportal based upon the information provided by partners on events to which the project is presented; key updates on the development of the platform; presentations, workshops and demonstrations; reports, publications and media interest.

The planned timetable for the distribution of the newsletters and planned contents, are the following:

Newsletter Nº 1. February-March 2017.

- Network presentation.
- Launch of Inventory of Smart Farming Technologies in Platform.
- Dates and details of the first round of Innovation Workshops in Innovation Hubs.
- News from Innovation Hubs: Operational Groups calls, Field Days, etc.
- Smart Farming related news and events at EU and global level.

Newsletter Nº 2. November-December 2017.

- Launch of Networking Area in Platform.
- Findings on the report on farmers needs and barriers for adopting smart farming
- Results on Innovation Workshops in Innovation Hubs.
- News from Innovation Hubs: Operational Groups calls, Field Days, etc.
- Smart Farming related news and events at EU and global level.

Newsletter Nº 3. May 2018.

- Final results from Innovation Workshops in Innovation Hubs and from transnational Workshop.
- Main recommendations from Smart AKIS for smart farming support at national and Eu level, extracted from Policy Briefs.
- News from Innovation Hubs: Operational Groups calls, Field Days, etc.
- Smart Farming related news and events at EU and global level.
- Legacy of Smart AKIS Network through EIP-AGRI Service Points after project's end.

Smart AKIS partners will be encouraged to forward the digital newsletter to those contacts who might be interested on the Network. An offline version of the newsletters will also be available in English and local languages in webportal.

2.4. Social media.

Smart AKIS Network will use social media with the following goals:

- Provide information for raising awareness on the Smart Farming benefits for target groups, latest trends and related events.
- Disseminate the project outputs, webportal services and events, as well as those from network partners related to Smart Farming.
- Engage stakeholders in the regional and transnational Innovation Workshops.

The following two social media tools will be used from the start of the project:

Facebook

The Smart AKIS Facebook fan page will be created in a public mode, under the community field, with the name “Smart AKIS – Smart Farming Network” and the short name @SmartFarmingNetwork. The official language of the posts uploaded to this page will be English, even though posts in other languages, mainly those of Innovation Hub partners will also be shared.

Figure 8. Smart AKIS Facebook page

INICIATIVAS INNOVADORAS will be the administrator of the Facebook page. The administrator's role is to manage all aspects of the page including messages dispatch and publication of posts, the confirmation of posts and comments, and the posting and sharing of events, including those of the Network, partners and other events of interest.

A brief description of the project will be added to the Facebook page in order to inform the general public about the objectives of the project. The link to the webportal will also display in the Facebook page.

Twitter

The Twitter account will be used as one of the primary tools in spreading the Network news and announcements. In the Twitter account, tweets will be uploaded in a regular base, referring to results and news, and any important information institutional or scientific that is relevant to the smart farming field.

The Twitter account @smart_akis.com will be a useful channel to immediately disseminate Network activities and news to a wide audience, as well as to raise awareness about the latest news and trends in the Smart Farming field, including the following:

- Internet of Things impact on agriculture.
- Agricultural Big Data.
- Open data.
- Drones and bots.
- Precision agriculture.
- Agtech investments & venture capital.
- Agriculture and agri-food value chain innovation.

Thus, the following hash tags will be consistently used on the Network publications: #Farmbots #agdrones #smartfarming #digitalfarming #farmnerds #smartagriculture #agtech and #EIPAgri.

Figure 9. Smart AKIS Twitter profile.

The official language of the tweets will be English, even though re-tweets might be made in English, from original tweets in other languages, mainly those of Innovation Hub partners will also be shared. Twitter account will be managed by INIATIVAS AINNOVADORAS. Account will follow not only main corporate and institutional players from academia, industry and national and EC agricultural field, but also individual accounts by influencers in the Smart Farming and Agricultural Innovation fields.

In order to achieve a relevant positioning and number of followers, the profiles will be linked with partners' social media profiles, as well as those from EIP-AGRI, other Thematic Networks, and smart farming influencers in a worldwide level, not limited to EU, but also bringing news and insights from the Smart Farming ecosystems in USA, Australia and Canada. A monthly monitoring on the number of followers and likes of the profiles will be conducted.

YouTube channel

A dedicated YouTube channel will be created and linked to the webportal in 2018, once the 5 videos produced in the framework of WP2 will be available, with well documented success cases of multi-actor innovation processes selected by partners.

Partners' social media profiles will also echo the Smart AKIS Network publications and the other way round, further increasing the combined impact and outreach of the Network:

Partner	Social media	Profile	Followers/Likes
AUA	Facebook	ESN AUA Athens	1.769
ACTA	Facebook	@arvalisinfos	1.763
	Facebook	@arvalisinstitutduvegetal	771
	Twitter	@ACTA_asso	412
	Twitter	@vignevinfrance	1.576
	Twitter	@Arvalisofficiel	1.381
BioSense	Twitter	@BioSenseRS	81
	Facebook	@biosense.institute	210
CEMA	Facebook	CEMA-European-Agricultural-Machinery	643
	Twitter	@CEMAagri	917
CUMA	Facebook	@salonnationalcuma	1.273
	Twitter	@FRcumaOuest	453
Delphy	Twitter	@DelphyEN	523
	Twitter	@DelphyNL	1.691
	Facebook	Delphy	430
DLG	Facebook	@DLGFeldtage	10.592
	Twitter	@DLGeV	3.192
Iniciativas Innovadoras	Twitter	@iniciativas_in	256
ZALF	Facebook	@zalf.agrarlandschaftsforschung	462

Table 7. Smart AKIS partners social media

2.5. Publicity materials

The following publicity materials will be elaborated and distributed, both in paper and digital versions, as in English and in Innovation Hubs languages.

Smart AKIS leaflet

A leaflet template will be produced at the start of the project, in English, in Word, with basic project information, available for partners to adapt and localise to their local contexts. This leaflet will allow disseminating the project before the Network brochure is available.

Figure 10. Smart AKIS leaflet

Smart AKIS roll-up

A roll-up template will also be available at the start of the project, open to be tailored to the partners' communication goals in local languages. The roll-ups will be produced locally by partners following the general template and consistently used in the framework of regional and transnational Innovation Workshops, dissemination of Network at partners' events and at events organised by other stakeholders.

Figure 11. Smart AKIS roll-up

Smart AKIS brochure

A brochure designed as a folder will be available on the first quarter of 2017 in English and local languages, to be locally printed by partners. It will deliver information on Network, partnership and future services, and it will be used on the regional and transnational Innovation Workshops as well as on any kind of networking or dissemination meeting and event.

Smart AKIS bookmark

A bookmark has also been designed in English, open to be localised to local language by partners, to be locally printed by partners. The bookmark is designed as a friendly reminder of the Network image, webportal and social media, and will also be disseminated in the framework of workshop, events and personal meetings with key stakeholders.

Figure 12. Smart AKIS Bookmark

3. Dissemination activities

3.1. Network Events.

All along the project, the following Network Events will be held:

21 Regional Innovation Multi-Actor Workshops

3 editions of Innovation Workshops with a multi-actor approach will be held in the framework of WP3 in France, Germany, Greece, Netherlands, Spain, Serbia and UK. All in all, 21 workshops will be held two at each location with the following estimated timetable:

- 1st regional Innovation Workshops: To be held between February and June 2017.
- 2nd regional Innovation Workshops: To be held between October and December 2017.
- 3rd regional Innovation Workshops: To be held between March and May 2018.

Network partners organising the events will have freedom to choose the most suitable dates following the local agendas. In spite of the technical nature of the Workshops focusing on the dissemination of the Smart Farming technologies assessed as most promising to the needs of the local farmer communities and to the identification and capture of project ideas leading to transfer and new development innovation projects, the workshops will also serve a dissemination purpose, as general information on the Network goals, activities and upcoming services will be presented.

Organisations in neighbouring regions and countries with the same language will also be invited. France will target Belgium and Switzerland; Germany will target Austria and Switzerland; Holland will target Belgium; DLV will target Poland through GreenQ, its subsidiary company. National machinery associations in CEMA will also attend. Whenever possible, Smart-AKIS partners will organize the dissemination workshops in connection to their “Open Field Days” so as to attract the broadest possible audience.

1 Transnational Innovation Multi-Actor Workshop

A transnational Innovation Workshop will be held in Serbia in February 2018, with representatives from the Multi-Actor communities from the Innovation Hubs. With the goal of exchanging thematic/sector projects and solutions and generating transnational project ideas. At this stage of the project, main dissemination messages will be linked to the future of the services put in place by the Network and its future integration and or link to the EIP-AGRI Service Point.

1 Smart AKIS Final Conference

A final dissemination event will be organized in connection to Smart AKIS final meeting in Brussels ideally as a satellite to a larger event, in June 2018. The final conference will raise awareness about the importance of AKIS in fostering innovation and the role of Smart Farming in contributing to a more sustainable and productive agriculture. Success stories related to the capturing of grassroots-level ideas, regional innovation processes and the links between Thematic Networks and Operational

Groups will also be presented. The event will be coordinated with other Thematic Networks and the EIP-AGRI.

3.2. Non-network events

The activities and results of Smart AKIS will also be presented in conferences, events and fairs in order to ensure timely and proper input and feedback by key stakeholders, while supporting the dissemination of the project results through the appropriate material.

A number of events have already been identified; we can differentiate between events held by partners on a regular basis, where Smart AKIS Network will be showcased, as well as events organised by other networks, initiatives, fairs, conferences, etc, where partners will actively disseminate the project, either through a presentation included on the event's programme, participation through a stand or the distribution of Network materials.

Partners' events.

Partner	Event	Place	Periodicity	Nº of participants
CEMA	CEMA Innovation Day	Brussels (BE)	Yearly	200
	CEMA Conference in SIMA tradeshow	Paris (FR)	Yearly	200
	CEMA Summit	Brussels (BE)	Yearly	300
ACTA	Les Assises des vins du Sud-Ouest	Toulouse (FR)	Yearly	300
	Les Culturelles Field Day and Conference	France	Every 2 years	12.000
CUMA	Mécaelevage Field Day	Yffiniac (FR)	Every 2 years	2.500
	Salon aux Champs field day	France	Every 2 years	10.000
David Tinker & Associates/EurAgEng	CIGR-AgEng Conference	Aarhus (DK)	June 2016	600
	FIMA EurAgEng Worekshop	Zaragoza (ES)	Feb. 2016	100
DLG	DLG-Feldtage Field Day	Germany	Every 2 years	30.000
	Agritechnica Fairtrade	Hannover (DE)	Every 2 years	450.000
	Intervitis Interfructa Hortitechnica	Stuttgart (DE)	Every 2 years	10.000
INTIA	GENVCE	Navarra (ES)	May-2017	200
	Arable Crops Results Day	Navarra (ES)	July- Yearly	100-150
	Summer horticulture Results Day	Navarra-(ES)	September- Yearly	100-150
	Autumn horticulture	Navarra	November-	100-150

	Results Day	(ES)	Yearly	
ZALF	ICROP2016	Berlin (DE)	March 2016	500

Table 8. Partners events

Other targeted events

Smart AKIS partners will also take part in international and local conferences, meetings, fairs, exhibitions, in order to disseminate the network and raise awareness on Smart Farming in Europe.

The table below provides a list of indicative relevant events already identified by partners. Some of them have already been the subject of Smart AKIS dissemination activities, like for instance the presentation of Smart AKIS in the framework of FIMA Fair in Zaragoza (Spain) in 2016. Other events are recurring ones and it is forth likely that partners will attend and actively disseminate the Network on such for a. INICIATIVAS INNOVADORAS will encourage the participation of partners on such events and will coordinate the partners efforts on this regard, ensuring that a proper dissemination of the Network takes place and that a report on the attendance is made available.

Event	Place	Periodicity	Nº of participants
FAIRS / EXHIBITIONS	Target Groups: Farmers & Industry		
SITEVI Fair	Montpellier (FR)	Every 2 years	50.000
VINITEC Fair	Bordeaux (FR)	Every 2 years	45.000
SIMA Fair	Paris (FR)	Every year	50.000
Danube IT	Novi Sad (SR)	Every year	150
Agricultural Fair	Novi Sad (SR)	Every year	500
Technology Fair	Belgrade (SR)	Every year	200
IPM Essen	Essen (DE)	Every year	1.000
Tuinbouwrelatiedagen	Gorinchem (NL)	Every year	800
Fruit Logistica	Berlin (DE)	Every year	1.000
GreenTech	Amsterdam (NL)	Every year	1.500
Onion Field Day	Coiljnsplaat / Zeeland (NL)	Every year	1.000
National Potato event	Zeeland (NL)	Every year	1.000
Field Event arable farming,	Zeijen / Drente (NL)	Every year	300
ATH (Agricultural Technology event Holland)	Biddinghuizen / Flevoland (NL)	Every year	20.000
FIMA	Zaragoza (ES)	Every year	5.000
Agrotica	Thessalonica (EL)	Every 2 years	40.000
Agri-Teach EAST REAP	Cambridge (UK)	Every year	500
SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES	Target Groups: Farmers, Research, Industry, Policymakers, R&I Networks		
Forum for the Future of Agriculture	Europe	Every year	500
COPA-COGECA Congress	Europe	Every year	5.000
European Conference on Precision Agriculture	Europe	Every 2 years	5.000
CAPIGI-Geoagri	Europe	Every year	1.000

International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies in Agriculture, Food and Environment (HAICTA 2015)	Europe	Every 2 years	500
IFAMA World Conference	World	Every year	3.000

Table 8. Other targeted events

Furthermore, an active participation and dissemination of the Network on events organised by EIP-AGRI, other thematic Networks, and national EIP Clusters will be arranged. Specifically, dissemination on the events organised by the following initiatives is planned:

- EIP-AGRI Workshops on subjects related to Agriculture IT, Precision Agriculture, Agricultural Big data, Earth Observation Systems, etc.
- Standing Committee for Agricultural Research (SCAR) Working Group on Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS).
- AIOTI: Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation events and assembly.
- Events organised from national EIP Clusters in France, Germany, Greece, Serbia, Spain, The Netherlands, and UK.
- Events held by National Rural Networks in France, Germany, Greece, Serbia, Spain, The Netherlands, and UK.
- Events held by Thematic Networks:
 - 4D4F: Smart Dairy farming.
 - AGRIFORVALOR: Biomass from agriculture and forest.
 - AGRISPIN: Innovation brokering in agriculture.
 - EUFRUIT: Fruit.
 - EURODAIRY: Dairy Farming.
 - FERTINNOWA: Water management in fertigated crops.
 - HENNOVATION: Poultry Farming.
 - HNV-LINK: High Nature Value Farming.
 - OK-NET ARABLE: Organic Farming.
 - WINETWORK: Wine growing.

3.3. Publications

All partners will actively promote the Network through the publication of ed/ops or articles on Network goals and results. Publications in two kinds of media can be differentiated:

Popular Publications on partners' media

The following mass media have been identified. The publication of periodic news on relation to the project progress will be coordinated between the Network Dissemination Officer and appointed partners' Dissemination Officers.

Partner	Media	Periodicity	Nº of subscribers
CEMA	Digital newsletter	12 a year	900

David Tinker & Associates/EurAgEng	Paper newsletter	Twice a year	2.000	
	Digital newsletter	10 a year	2.500	
ACTA	ACTA internal digital newsletter	12 a year		
	ACTA external digital newsletter	2 a year		
	IFV digital newsletter	4 a year	9.600	
	IFV digital newsletter	5 a year	2.000	
	ARVALIS digital newsletter Yvoir	Daily	12.500	
	ARVALIS digital newsletter Infos	Weekly	54.000	
	IFV La grappe d'Autan magazine	4 a year	2.000	
	ARVALIS Perspectives Agricoles magazine	12 a year	16.000	
	ARVALIS Terres Inovia infos magazine	4-6 a year	20.000	
	CUMA	Entraid digital magazine	12 a year	
	Delphy	Digital and paper newsletter	Every 1-2 weeks	5.000
Annual report		Yearly	3.000	
Boerderij paper magazine		Weekly	30.000	
Nieuwe Oogst magazine		Weekly	50.000	
	Landbouwmechanisatie magazine	Weekly	10.000	
DLG	Digital newsletter	Weekly	20.000	
INTIASA	Digital newsletter	15 days	300	
	Digital & paper magazine	Quarterly	300	
ZALF	Digital newsletter	Monthly	300	

Table 9. Partners mass media

Popular articles in specialised magazines

Main publications issued from the Smart-AKIS project will be popular articles in farmers, extension services and industry magazines. Local extension magazines will play a key role in disseminating SFT information tailored to the specific regions. The following farmers', professional and advisors magazines will be targeted: Agrinnovation (the new magazine of the EC's DG for Agriculture and Rural Development), Boerderij, Nieuw Oogst, Ekoland, Akker Magazine (Netherlands); Perspectives Agricoles, La France Agricole, Entraid' (France); DLG Nachrichten, DLG Mitteilungen, Top Agrar, Landtechnikmagazine (Germany), Agricultura, Agrotécnica (Spain), Profi (several European versions), Farmers Weekly, Farmers Guardian, Landwards, (UK. Journalists from these magazines will be invited to the regional/national workshops for reporting on the events.

The publication of periodic news on relation to the project progress will be coordinated between the Network Dissemination Officer and appointed partners' Dissemination Officers, who will report in turn all the pieces of news published in specialised magazines.

3.4. Press releases.

Press releases will be produced as relevant pieces of news on project main milestones. Network related press releases will be elaborated by INICIATIVAS INNOVADORAS, and translated in turn by partner to local languages. If the press releases are related to a specific event, host partner will be charged with the local distribution of the press release among national mass media. Press releases will also be produced and distributed by Innovation Hub partners with occasion of the holding of the Innovation Workshops.

The elaboration and distribution of the following press releases is planned:

- Network launch with occasion of project kick-off meeting (1).
- Launch of Inventory of Smart Farming Solutions (1).
- Findings of reports addressing the farmers' needs and barriers for adopting smart farming in Europe (1).
- Holding of regional Innovation Workshops in 7 Innovation Hubs (7).
- Holding of transnational Innovation workshop in Serbia (1).
- Smart AKIS Recommendations for Smart Farming adoption in Europe (1 general + 7 national).
- Smart AKIS Final Conference (1).

Press releases will be distributed through the following channels:

- Network webportal and social media.
- EU and national wide electronic media platform related to Agriculture & Smart Farming: EIP-AGRI, National Rural Networks, Thematic Network websites, COPA-COGECA, European Landowners Association, EurActiv, Farmers Weekly, EFEAgro, etc.
- Localised version of press releases to be distributed through their websites, social media and specialised agriculture related platforms.

3.5. Networking and person to person meetings.

In order to engage stakeholders more directly, personal interaction will also be a key means for dissemination. Personal interaction will mainly take place at the multi-actor Innovation Workshops and the trade fairs, exhibitions, workshops and conferences identified in section 3.2.

This category of dissemination will also include all the clustering activities with other European and funded projects related to Smart Farming, Agricultural Innovation Systems, Key technologies impacting on Smart Farming such as Internet of Things, Earth Observation Systems, Big Data, drones and robotics, etc, identified in section 3.3.

All partners will be engaged in such going networking and person to person meetings, duly reporting such progress to Network Dissemination Officer through the delivery of six-monthly Dissemination Activity Report, in order to keep track on the number of target groups reached.

Aware of the huge number of potential stakeholders to be engaged both at national and EU level, partners have identified in the framework of the Target Groups mapping effort described in section 1.4, those target groups deemed as Key , which will be the main target for the arrangement of person to person meetings.

4. Dissemination Work Plan

4.1. Dissemination governance

All Smart AKIS partners are experienced in the implementation of Research & Innovation project at EU level, and are this committed and aware on the importance of the dissemination on such projects, more even in the case of Smart AKIS, whose main goal is the dissemination and transfer of available Smart Farming technologies. Thus, all partners will rely on their accumulated dissemination experience and tools in order to achieve the highest impact of the Network.

INCIATIVAS INNOVADORAS is the leader of Work package 5, but all partners will be engaged on the on-going dissemination of the Network. Thus, INCIATIVAS INNOVADORAS will mainly play a Coordinator/Facilitator role, ensuring that the Dissemination Strategy and Plan is collectively implemented by all partners.

To that end, The Dissemination Strategy will be implemented by all partners, following a governance system composed of the following bodies:

- Network Dissemination Officer.
- Network Dissemination Group.
- Partners Dissemination Officers.

Network Dissemination Officer

Network Dissemination Officer will be Natalia Bellostas from INCIATIVAS INNOVADORAS.

Natalia Bellostas

Natalia holds a PhD in Biochemistry and a MSc in Agroecology from the University of Copenhagen (Denmark) and is Agronomist from the Public University of Navarra (Spain). She has broad experience in R&I activities in Agriculture and Environment, as well as in the definition and coordination of R&I projects at European level. She has participated as external coordinator in ATLANT-KIS, where she has developed broad expertise in cross-border collaborations in innovation. She has been involved in the drafting and the coordination of several successful Coordination and Support Actions and Research and Innovation Actions funded under Horizon 2020 in the agricultural field, such as Smart-AKIS, RECAP, PROTEIN2FOOD.

Her role will be the following:

- Planning and coordination of dissemination activities with appointed Dissemination Officers on a six month basis.
- Reporting on dissemination activities compiling the information received from Dissemination Officers on a six month basis.
- Webportal content management: news & events.
- Social media community manager: Facebook & Twitter.

- Edition of 3 digital newsletters with the contribution from Dissemination Officers.
- Coordination of the publicity materials design and layout and printing (by partners).
- Coordination of the participation of Smart AKIS partners on non-network targeted events.
- Presentation of Smart AKIS Network at non-network targeted events and to key stakeholders through personal meetings.
- Coordination with Dissemination Officers the publication of popular articles on partners' media and on specialised magazines.
- Elaboration of Network related press releases and coordination of local press releases by Dissemination Officers.
- Coordination of the programme and logistics, with AUA, of Smart AKIS Final Conference.

Dissemination Work Group

The Dissemination Work Group will be composed by 4 partners, with key responsibilities on the overall running of the Network, and specifically on its dissemination activities:

- INICIATIVAS INNOVADORAS: As WP5, Dissemination Coordinator.
- AUA: As general Coordinator of the Network.
- BioSense: As WP4 Leader, in charge of the development and running of the Smart Community platform, where network webportal and main services for target groups will be hosted.
- ACTA: As partner in charge of the networking responsibilities with EIP-AGRI.

The Dissemination Work Group will meet through a Skype meeting each six-month with the following goals:

- Review or update if necessary of the overall Dissemination Strategy & Plan.
- Review and agreement on the Dissemination Work Plan elaborated by Network Dissemination Officer.
- Review and agreement Dissemination Activity Report compiled with the whole of activities conducted in the previous semester by Network Dissemination Officer.

Any decisions on regards to the update or review of the current Dissemination plan or of the planned activities will be reached by the Work Group, and shared with the rest of the consortium in the Steering Group.

Partners Dissemination Officers

All partners have appointed a Dissemination Officer:

Partner	Name	Last name
AUA	Matina	Voulgaraki
DLO	Hein	ten Berge
ZALF	Maria	Kernecker
BIOS	Milica	Trajkovic
ACTA	Pauline	Bodin
INTIA	Isabel	Gárriz
DLG	Klaus	Erdle

Delphy	Mathilde	van Werven
	Harm	Brink
APV	Borislav	Brunet
INI	Ion	Gorriti
CEMA	Beatriz	Arribas
CUMA	Fabien	Valorge
	Rozenn	Le Guellec
DTA	David	Tinker

Table 10. Partners Dissemination Officers.

On a day to day basis, the Network Dissemination Officer will closely coordinate with such interlocutors through telephone, email and Skype. Besides this on-going communication, Dissemination Network Officer will send each 2-3 weeks a Dissemination Update (an email) to partners' Dissemination Officers, with a review and recap of the dissemination activities already implemented and those to be implemented in the following weeks, following the agreed Dissemination Work Plan.

The role of Dissemination Officers will be the following:

- Production of localised publicity materials: translation, localisation and printing of leaflet, brochure, roll-up and bookmark.
- Dissemination of Network activities on partners' mass media and on specialized magazines.
- Delivery of pieces of news and events of interest to Network Dissemination Officer for feeding up the webportal, social media and digital newsletters.
- Presentation of Smart AKIS Network at non-network targeted events and to key stakeholders through personal meetings.
- Proposal of dissemination activities to be conducted each semester and reporting of dissemination activities implemented by the delivery to Network Dissemination Officer of Dissemination Activity Reports.
- Elaboration of local press releases.

In order to facilitate communication and interaction with Innovation Hubs, a single Contact Point has been appointed by Innovation Hub. S/he will be receiving all the requests of information on regards to the activities planned by Smart AKIS at each Innovation Hub, mainly the Innovation Workshops:

Innovation Hub	Contact Point	Partner
France	Pauline Bodin	ACTA
Germany	Klaus Erdle	DLG
Greece	Matina Voulgaraki	AUA
Serbia	Milica Trajkovic	BioSense
Spain	Alberto Lafarga	INTIASA
The Netherlands	Harm Brinks	Delphy
UK	David Tinker	David Tinker & Associates

Table 11. Innovation Hub Contact Points

4.2. Dissemination planning

Network Dissemination Officer will elaborate each six months a Dissemination Work Plan taking into consideration the overall time plan described in following pages, as well as Dissemination Officers contributions. Dissemination Work Plan will be reviewed and agreed by Dissemination Work Group.

Contents of the Work Plan will be very simple, and are included on Annex 5.3:

- Description of the activities to be carried out following a set of categories, with indication of the expected time for their implementation and the partners responsible for carrying them out.
- A Gantt chart with indication of the timeline of the activities planned.

Figure 13. Dissemination Work Plan template

Indicative work plan by semesters:

Semester 1. March – August 2016.

Activity	Date
DISSEMINATION STRATEGY & PLAN	
Target Groups analysis and assessment of partners’ dissemination tools	June 2016
Elaboration of Dissemination Plan	August 2016
Definition of Dissemination Work Plan Semester 1 & 2	August 2016
DISSEMINATION TOOLS	

Network Visual Identity	March 2016
Launch of Network webportal	June 2016
Creation of Social media accounts	June 2016
Graphic design of leaflet, roll-up and bookmark templates	May 2016
DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	
Press release: Kick-off meeting	March 2016
Participation at non-network targeted events	March-August 2016
Publication of popular articles	March-August 2016
Networking and person to person meetings	March-August 2016

Table 12. Work Plan Semester 1

Semester 2. September 2016 – February 2017.

Activity	Date
DISSEMINATION STRATEGY & PLAN	
Dissemination Work Group meeting	September 2016
Delivery of Dissemination Updates (email)	Sept- 2016 – Feb. 2017
Elaboration of Dissemination Report Semester 1	September 2016
Definition of Dissemination Work Plan Semester 3	Feb. 2017
DISSEMINATION TOOLS	
Update of Network webportal with news & events feeds	Sept- 2016 – Feb. 2017
Management of social media accounts	Sept- 2016 – Feb. 2017
Graphic design and printing of Network brochure	Sept- 2016 – Feb. 2017
DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	
Participation at non-network targeted events	Sept- 2016 – Feb. 2017
Publication of popular articles	Sept- 2016 – Feb. 2017
Networking and person to person meetings	Sept- 2016 – Feb. 2017

Table 13. Work Plan Semester 2

Semester 3. March – August 2017.

Activity	Date
DISSEMINATION STRATEGY & PLAN	
Dissemination Work Group meeting	March 2017
Delivery of Dissemination Updates (email)	March – August 2017
Elaboration of Dissemination Report Semester 2	March 2017
Definition of Dissemination Work Plan Semester 4	August 2017
DISSEMINATION TOOLS	
Update of Network webportal with news & events feeds	March – August 2017
Management of social media accounts	March – August 2017
Edition and distribution of digital newsletter Nº 1	March 2017
DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	
Press releases: launch of Inventory of Smart Farming solutions, findings	March 2017

from farmers' needs report and holding of Innovation Workshops	
Holding of 1 st round of Innovation Workshops at 7 Innovation Hubs	March – June 2017
Participation at non-network targeted events	Sept- 2016 – Feb. 2017
Publication of popular articles	Sept- 2016 – Feb. 2017
Networking and person to person meetings	Sept- 2016 – Feb. 2017

Table 14. Work Plan Semester 3

Semester 4. September 2017 – February 2018.

Activity	Date
DISSEMINATION STRATEGY & PLAN	
Dissemination Work Group meeting	September 2017
Delivery of Dissemination Updates (email)	Sept. 2017 – Feb. 2018.
Elaboration of Dissemination Report Semester 3	September 2017
Definition of Dissemination Work Plan Semester 5	Feb. 2018
DISSEMINATION TOOLS	
Update of Network webportal with news & events feeds	Sept. 2017 – Feb. 2018.
Management of social media accounts	Sept. 2017 – Feb. 2018.
Edition and distribution of digital newsletter N ^o 2	November 2017
DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	
Holding of 2 nd round of Innovation Workshops at 7 Innovation Hubs	Oct. – Dec. 2017
Holding of transnational Innovation Workshop in Serbia	Feb. 2018
Participation at non-network targeted events	Sept. 2017 – Feb. 2018.
Publication of popular articles	Sept. 2017 – Feb. 2018.
Networking and person to person meetings	Sept. 2017 – Feb. 2018.

Table 15. Work Plan Semester 4

Semester 5. March – August 2018

Activity	Date
DISSEMINATION STRATEGY & PLAN	
Dissemination Work Group meeting	March 2018
Delivery of Dissemination Updates (email)	March – August 2018
Elaboration of Dissemination Report Semester 4	March 2018
DISSEMINATION TOOLS	
Update of Network webportal with news & events feeds	March – August 2018
Management of social media accounts	March – August 2018
Edition and distribution of digital newsletter N ^o 3	May 2018
DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	
Holding of 3 rd round of Innovation Workshops at 7 Innovation Hubs	March – May 2018
Holding of Smart AKIS Final Conference	June 2018
Participation at non-network targeted events	March – August 2018

Publication of popular articles	March – August 2018
Networking and person to person meetings	March – August 2018

Table 16. Work Plan Semester 5

4.3. Dissemination monitoring system

A dissemination monitoring system is proposed in order to provide evidence on the following fields:

- If Dissemination Plan is being implemented as initially planned and scheduled, in terms of Network Deliverables and Output Indicators.
- If Dissemination Plan objectives are being met in terms of Results Indicators.

The intention is to correct any deviation from the dissemination objectives, and to improve the performance of such activities as well as facilitate its evaluation. In order to set up an effective monitoring system, a clear connection between objectives and indicators needs to be established taking into consideration all arrangements needed to timely collect evidence that meet reporting requirements.

Network Deliverables

Following the Document of Work annexed to the project's Grant Agreement, under WP5 the following Deliverables are planned:

Deliverable (number)	Deliverable name	WP number	Lead participant	Type	Dissemination level	Delivery date
5.1	Dissemination Plan	5	INI	R	PU	M3
5.2	Dissemination Materials	5	INI	R	PU	M6
5.3	Smart-AKIS Events and general Dissemination activities	5	INI	R	PU	M15,24,30
5.4	Report on OGs and recommendations to link with TN	3	ACTA	R	PU	M30

Table 17. Work Package 5 Deliverables

The number and expected delivery time of such Deliverables have been considered as Output Indicators included on the Balanced Scorecard described in next section. At the time being, no delays on their delivery is expected.

Balanced Scorecard with Output & Result Indicators

In order to assess the success of the Dissemination Plan, a set of Key Target Indicators have been selected, extracted from the Output and Results indicators

These indicators have been integrated into a Dissemination Balanced Scorecard with a description of the indicator, the method of measurement, the verification means, the owner of the indicator, the

periodicity on which it will be monitored and the target value planned. The descriptive Balanced Scorecard is attached in Annex 5.6; the following table summarises the Key Target Indicators and their target values.

INDICATOR	CATEGORY OF INDICATOR	TARGET VALUE
DISSEMINATION STRATEGY & PLAN		
Dissemination Plan	Output	1
Nº of meetings of Dissemination Work Group	Output	5
Nº of Dissemination Work Plans	Output	5
Nº of six-monthly Dissemination Reports	Output	5
Nº of annual Dissemination Reports	Output	3
Nº of Dissemination Updates distributed	Output	30
DISSEMINATION TOOLS		
Nº of webportal	Output	1
Nº of social media accounts	Output	3
Nº of publicity materials	Output	4
Nº of digital newsletters distributed	Output	3
Nº of webportal visitors	Result	1.000
Nº of webportal pages visited	Result	2.000
Nº of Twitter followers	Result	1.000
Nº of Facebook page likes	Result	500
Nº of Facebook page visits	Result	100
Nº of people outreached by Facebook page	Result	1.000
Nº of people outreached by digital newsletter	Result	3.000
Nº of people outreached with publicity materials	Result	2.500
Nº of stakeholders from Innovation Hubs registered on the Platform	Result	700
Nº of stakeholders from other EU countries registered on the Platform	Result	2.500
Nº of visits to Smart Farming Community Platform	Result	2.000
DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES		
Nº of regional Innovation Workshops held	Output	21
Nº of open transnational Innovation Workshops held	Output	1
Nº of Network Final Conference held	Output	1

Nº of non-network events where Network has been disseminated	Output	50
Nº of popular articles published in partners' media	Output	50
Nº of popular articles published in specialized media	Output	30
Nº of press releases issued	Output	20
Nº of participants on regional Innovation Workshops	Result	700
Nº of participants on transnational Innovation Workshop	Result	60
Nº of participants on Final Conference	Result	60
Nº of people outreached at non-network events	Result	1.250
Nº of policy makers reached with recommendations and policy briefs	Result	100
Nº of Thematic Networks coordinated with	Result	8
Nº of Operational Groups and national EIP clusters coordinated with	Result	50

Table 18. Dissemination Balances Scorecard summary table

Dissemination Reporting

The reporting of dissemination activities will take place at three levels:

Nº	Report	Responsible	Periodicity
1	Partners' Dissemination Report	All partners	Six-monthly
2	Six-monthly Network Dissemination Report compiling partners' contributions	INI	Six-monthly
3	Annual Dissemination Report – Project Deliverable	INI	M15, M24, M30

Partners' Dissemination Report

Each six months Dissemination Officers from partners will send Network Dissemination Officer a compilation of the dissemination activities carried out by the partner, providing evidence and support materials of the activities carried out (press clippings, programmes, pictures, etc).

To that end a template has been elaborated, attached in Annex 5.4 allowing to simply providing requested information on the following fields:

- Nº of publicity materials produced distributed.
- Nº and outreach of popular publications and press releases on partners' media.
- Nº and outreach of popular publications and press releases on specialised media.
- Nº and outreach of Network and non-network targeted events.
- Nº of key target groups/networks outreached through person to person meetings.

For each of the reported dissemination activities partners will have to provide some simple information filling in a Fact Sheet to be accompanied with supporting documents.

Figure 14. Partners Dissemination Report template

Network Dissemination Report

Network Dissemination Officer will compile Partners Dissemination Reports and produce semestrially and annually a Network Dissemination Report. The scope and impact of the carried out activities will be assessed by the Dissemination Work Group.

The contents of the Dissemination Report will be the following, as included in Annex 5.5:

- Listing of all the dissemination activities carried out by the Network and partners, supported by the respective Fact Sheets with detailed information.
- Update of the Balanced Scorecard with indication of the level of achievements of the target value of expected Output and Results Indicators.

The annual Dissemination Report will be Deliverable to be submitted to the EC following the Grant Agreement.

5. Annexes

- 5.1. Visual Identity Handbook.
- 5.2. Webportal architecture.
- 5.3. Dissemination Work Plan template.
- 5.4. Partners Dissemination Report template.
- 5.5. Network Dissemination Report template
- 5.6. Dissemination Balanced Scorecard.

SMART AKIS

Manual de identidad corporativa

Índice

- 1. El logotipo**
- 2. Los colores corporativos**
- 3. Tipografía**
- 4. Versiones del logotipo**
- 5. Versiones no permitidas del logotipo**
- 6. Legibilidad y protección**

1. Logotipo

El proyecto SMART AKIS tiene su base en 3 conceptos principales: red de colaboración, tecnología y sector agrario.

La imagen de **SMART AKIS** se ha configurado a partir de dos elementos gráficos:

- **Una red de trabajo conectada y dinámica.**

La imagen de la red de socios tiene a su vez un tratamiento gráfico que la asocia a una gran antena, orientada a recoger datos para el desarrollo del proyecto. Proyecta tanto la idea de tecnología como de cooperación.

- **El fruto del trabajo en equipo, representado por el brote.**

La imagen del brote -más bucólica- representa la consecución de un objetivo, así como su vinculación estrecha con el entorno en el que está enmarcado el proyecto: el sector agrario.

El logotipo puede usarse igualmente con el lema "Smart Farming Thematic Network" o sin él.

smart **AKIS**
Smart Farming Thematic Network

smart **AKIS**

2. Colores corporativos

Partimos de dos premisas:

- El color verde resulta imprescindible para proyectar la imagen del sector agrario.
- El sector agrario debe estar asociado a un concepto fundamental: la vida.

Desde esa premisa se ha buscado una combinación del verde con un color cálido que aporte fuerza y luz a la marca, es decir, vida.

El color naranja, además de aportar cierto recuerdo al elemento "tierra", cumple con esos requisitos cromáticos deseados.

2.1. CMYK

	Naranja C= 0 M=50 Y=100 K=0
	Verde C= 50 M=10 Y=100 K=10
	Gris C= 0 M=0 Y=0 K=70
	Gris C= 0 M=0 Y=0 K=20

2.2. RGB

	Naranja R= 225 G=115 B=30
	Verde R= 110 G=150 B=50
	Gris R= 75 G=75 B=75
	Gris R= 190 G=190 B=190

2.3. Tinta directa

	Naranja Pantone 144
	Verde Pantone 377

3. Tipografía

La tipografía del logotipo pertenece a la familia **"Gotham"**. Se ha elegido la variante "light" para la palabra "smart" y la variante "Medium" para el acrónimo "AKIS".

El lema "Smart Farming Thematic Network" utiliza tipografía **"Knowledge"**, de características similares a la "Gotham", pero más estrecha, lo que permite ampliar el tamaño del lema y hacerlo más legible en el conjunto de la marca.

Tipografías auxiliares

Por tratarse de un proyecto colaborativo, en el que intervienen diferentes agentes independientes, se aconseja utilizar una tipografía universal para el desarrollo de los documentos de SMART AKIS: informes, presentaciones, convocatorias, etc.

Cualquier fuente común a la mayoría de los sistemas operativos es válida, preferentemente: arial, helvetica,...

Podrán ser utilizadas tanto como título como para texto.

GOTHAM LIGHT

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

GOTHAM MEDIUM

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

KNOWLEDGE

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

4. Versiones del logotipo

Utilizaremos preferentemente la versión en positivo de nuestro logotipo sobre fondo blanco.

Cualquier tono o porcentaje de negro (hasta el 50%) es válido para la versión monocromática en positivo.

En caso de aplicar el logotipo sobre un fondo de color tendremos en cuenta lo siguiente:

- Siempre utilizaremos el logotipo en versión monocromática (blanco).
- Elegiremos, siempre que sea posible, un fondo corporativo: naranja, verde, negro/ gris.
- En caso de que el logotipo sea aplicado sobre una imagen o fotografía se aconseja -salvo que la imagen ofrezca un contraste suficiente- colocar un recuadro en tono anaranjado oscuro (con efecto "multiplicar" o "transparencia") sobre la imagen y bajo el logotipo, tal como puede observarse en el ejemplo.

5. Versiones no permitidas del logotipo

No están permitidos los siguientes supuestos:

- Alterar los colores de los elementos de la marca.
- Utilizar versiones monocromáticas que sean diferentes al negro o a un porcentaje de negro inferior al 50% (versión en positivo) o al blanco (versión en negativo).
- Utilizar la versión monocromática en negativo (blanco) sobre fondos de color no corporativos, o sobre imágenes que no permitan un contraste suficiente con el logotipo y, por tanto, dificulten su legibilidad.

Nota: en caso de que la aplicación del logotipo sobre un fondo de color sea ajena a nuestro control, se rogará que utilicen siempre la versión monocromática blanca o negra en función del tono de fondo y del buen criterio del diseñador.

6. Legibilidad y protección

Legibilidad

Con el objetivo de hacer legible el logotipo en su totalidad, se recomienda no reducir nunca las dimensiones que mostramos a continuación.

Tamaño mínimo

Protección

El perímetro del logotipo debe protegerse creando una "zona limpia" que impida la cercanía de elementos "invasores". Para ello tendremos en cuenta:

- Tomaremos como referencia la distancia entre la parte superior e inferior de los textos (logotipo y lema).
- Aplicaremos esa misma distancia hacia arriba y hacia abajo desde los límites superior e inferior de los textos.
- Aplicaremos esa misma distancia a izquierda y derecha desde los límites que marca el propio logotipo.

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SMART AKIS PARTNERS:

Smart AKIS Webportal Architecture

smart**AKIS**
Smart Farming Thematic Network

Document Summary

Deliverable Title: Smart AKIS Webportal Architecture

Version: Version 1.

Deliverable Lead: Iniciativas Innovadoras

Related Work package: Work package 4

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Contributor(s): All partners

Reviewer(s): To be determined

Communication level: PU Public

Grant Agreement Number: 696294

Project name: SMART AKIS

Start date of Project: March 2016

Duration: 36 Months

Project coordinator: University of Athens

Abstract

Working document with proposal of general requirements, design and the architecture of the Smart AKIS Network's webportal.

Table of Contents

1. General information	4
2. Webportal design	4
3. Webportal architecture	5
4. Webportal content delivery	10

1. General information

- Domain: www.smart-akis.com has been protected. Other options to consider might be: www.smartakis.eu, www.smartfarming.eu, www.smartfarmingnet.eu.
- Languages: Smart AKIS webportal's main language will be English, but some static information will also be available in partners' languages. Partners will have to contribute to the translation of such text.
- Content Management System (CMS): BioSense will use Joomla as webportal's CMS, that will be solely used by INI, who will propose on the Dissemination Plan a simple procedure for the update of the webportal with the contribution of partners' Communication Officers, mainly on the NEWS section.
- Smart Farming Community Platform: Smart AKIS webportal will play 2 main roles: 1) Communication and dissemination of the project and 2) main entry point to the Smart Farming Community platform services by end-users. Thus, when visiting the webportal, access to the Platform's services has to be made easy, quick and intuitive.
- Links: Partners will ensure good cross-linking between the webportal and their own sites. INI will also ensure that crosslinks are established with other Thematic Networks.
- Social media: Webportal will include links to the Smart AKIS Network social media profiles (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and Youtube), managed by INI. Twitter will probably be the most efficient social media taking into consideration the efforts implied on its update and potential impact, so a Twitterwall will be showcased.
- Digital newsletter: 3 digital newsletters will be distributed through MailChimp. Subscription of the distribution list will be possible through the webportal.
- Contact: Users and visitors will be able to contact the network at 2 levels: 1) general information by filling in an online form to be sent to INI and 2) information on Smart AKIS activities at innovation hub level, to be directed to appointed Innovation Hub Contact Points.
- Registration as users: If access to the Smart Farming Community Platform demands the registration of users, this function will be included once these have accessed the Smart Community platform services.
- Search engine positioning and web traffic analytics: BioSense will manage both tasks following its expertise on these fields, use frequently used keyword search phrases both in the metadata and in the contents pages.

2. Webportal design

- BioSense will develop the overall design of the webportal inspired by the Smart AKIS logo and image handbook.
- A simple and attractive design based upon the use of a streamlined menu with few sections, images and infographics is proposed.
- Some kind of visual or design link with EIP-AGRI webportal might be a good approach in order to mentally link both initiatives.

- A review of the webportal of current EIP-AGRI Thematic Networks show a wide variety of approaches, from very simplistic to more complex and layered architectures. Nonetheless, almost in all of them user experience remain a challenge:
 - Winetwork: <http://www.winetwork.eu/>
 - OK-Net Arable: <http://www.ok-net-arable.eu/>
 - HNV-Link: <http://www.high-nature-value-farming.eu/>
 - Hennovation: <http://www.hennovation.eu/>
 - Fertinnowa: <http://www.fertinnowa.com/>
 - EuroDairy: <http://www.eurodairy.eu>
 - Eufruit: <http://www.eufrin.org>
 - Agrispin: <http://agrispin.eu/>
 - Agriforvalor: <http://www.agriforvalor.eu/>
- Some webportals with simple and neat designs, that have inspired proposed architecture:
 - EIP-AGRI: <http://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/>
 - SUDOE Transnational Cooperation Programme: <http://www.interreg-sudoe.eu/>
 - EuroDairy Thematic Network: <http://eurodairy.eu/>
 - ROVINA project: <http://www.rovina-project.eu/>
 - CARER+: <http://www.carerplus.eu/>
 - Food Valley: <http://www.foodvalley.nl/eng/>
 - Brainport Development: <http://www.brainport.nl/en/>
 - ZALF: <http://www.zalf.de/en/Pages/ZALF.aspx>

3. Webportal architecture

HOMEPAGE

The screenshot shows the smartAKIS homepage layout with the following numbered annotations:

- 1:** Language selection menu (EN, ES, EE, FR, IE, DE, NL, SR)
- 2:** Main navigation menu (HOME, NETWORK, NEWS, SMART FARMING PLATFORM, MEDIA, CONTACT) and social media icons (Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn)
- 3:** smartAKIS logo
- 4:** Hero image banner showing a field with a drone and smartAKIS branding
- 5:** "What is Smart Farming?" section
- 6:** "I am a" section with user role buttons: Farmer, Agricultural advisor, Researcher, Provider of SFT solutions
- 7:** News section with a list of articles and three featured headline images with dates (03 MAY 2016, 29 ABR 2016, 14 MAR 2016)
- 8:** Smart Farming Community Platform section with buttons for "Inventory of SFT solutions" and "Networking area"
- 9:** Smart AKIS Partners section displaying logos of various organizations
- 10:** Footer area with "Map Contact Legal Notice Private area Links"
- 11:** EIP-AGRI logo

SECTIONS/AREAS

Nº 1. LANGUAGES:

Top right side, acronyms of the project languages with links to the respective pages: EN, ES, EE, FR, DE, NL, SR.

Nº 2. SOCIAL MEDIA:

Logos and links to Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter and Youtube profiles.

Nº 3. NAVIGATION BAR:

When moving mouse over section's name, each SECTION will vertically display a menu, that when selected will link to a new page.

Once in the page of a subsection, horizontal navigation bar will remain displayed but a new vertical navigation bar will be displayed on the page left side, with links to all the subsection pages of the corresponding section.

HOME	NETWORK	NEWS	SMART FARMING PLATFORM	MEDIA	CONTACT
	Smart AKIS				
	What is Smart Farming?				
	EIP-AGRI & Thematic Networks				
	Partners				
	Innovation Hubs				
	Results				

NETWORK/Smart AKIS

- Static text on all languages. To be provided by INI and translated by partners.
- Description of project goals and results.
- Info graphic with a description of the overall project approach and activities, leading to the Smart Community Platform Platform services.

NETWORK/What is Smart Farming?

- Static text on all languages.
- Description of Smart Farming: To be provided by INI and AUA and translated by partners.
 - Overall description of Smart Farming.
 - Description of 3 fields of SFT with an example: 1) farm management information systems, 2) precision agriculture and 3) automation and robotics.
 - Info graphic with a description of Smart Farming on a farm.
- Links to additional resources on SFT.

NETWORK/EIP-AGRI and Thematic Networks.

- Static text on all languages. To be provided by INI and translated by partners.
- Description and link to EIP-AGRI.

- Description of what are Thematic Networks and links to existing Networks.
- Description of what are Operational Groups and the role of Innovation Brokers.

NETWORK/Partners

- Static information in English. To be provided by partners.
- Main page with all logos and names of partners.
- When clicking on name and logo you get redirected to a new page with partner's information.

NETWORK/Innovation Hubs

- Static text on all languages. To be provided by INI and translated by partners.
- Map with the location of the 7 innovation hubs created in Smart-AKIS, including information on existing Operational Groups and funding calls.
- Information provided on the role of innovation hubs on the project, mainly on WP2 and WP3, and how stakeholders can participate and benefit.
- Information provided on the main Contact Point details for each innovation hub.

NETWORK/Results

- Access to public Deliverables of interest for target groups, once available:
 - Report on farmers' needs, innovative ideas and interests (WP2).
 - Report on factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion processes (WP2).
 - Multimedia material (WP2).
 - Overall Smart AKIS Report with results from the interactive workshops in 7 innovation hubs (WP3).
 - Report with opportunities for funding cross-border collaboration in innovation projects in SFT (WP3).
 - Smart AKIS Recommendations on SFT (WP3).
 - Policy Report and Briefs (WP3).
 - Scientific publications, if any (WP5).

HOME	NETWORK	NEWS	SMART FARMING PLATFORM	MEDIA	CONTACT
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When clicking on the section, you are redirected to a new page with 3 main sections:

NEWS

- The 3 latest news are displayed following tiles / blocks. When clicking on the news, a new page opens with the piece of news.
- Below, a link to "All News" is displayed. When clicking, you are redirected to a new page with all news displayed chronologically as a list of headlines with the date of the news.

EVENTS

- The 3 latest events, either of the project or from other organisations are displayed, following tiles/blocks.
- Below, a link to "All Events" is displayed. When clicking, you are redirected to a new page with all events displayed chronologically as a list of headlines with the date of the event.

NEWSLETTER

- Once available, the downloadable version of the newsletter files to be displayed for download.
- A field for subscribing to newsletter, to be managed through MailChimp.

HOME	NETWORK	NEWS	SMART FARMING PLATFORM	MEDIA	CONTACT
			Inventory of SFT Solutions		
			Networking area		

SMART FARMING PLATFORM/Home page

- Static text on all languages. Text to be provided by BioSense and translated by partners.
- For the time being, just a general home page with a description of the future services and functionalities of the platform.
- Once services are available, direct links to such pages will be included on the vertical navigation bar and on the general page.

HOME	NETWORK	NEWS	SMART FARMING PLATFORM	MEDIA	CONTACT
------	---------	------	------------------------	-------	---------

MEDIA:

- Page with following sections:
 - PRESS RELEASES: Downloadable version of press releases issued.
 - SMART AKIS PROJECT INFO:
 - ✓ Brochure: Downloadable version of project brochure in English and different languages.
 - ✓ Leaflet: Downloadable version of project brochure in English and different languages.
 - ✓ Project brief: PowerPoint presentation PDF-ed of project in English.
 - RECOMMENDATIONS: Policy and Recommendations Brief: Once deliverables of WP3 are available.
 - IMAGES: Gallery of copyright free pictures by partners.

- VIDEOS: Videos developed in WP3 once they are available.

HOME	NETWORK	NEWS	SMART FARMING PLATFORM	MEDIA	CONTACT
-------------	----------------	-------------	-------------------------------	--------------	----------------

When clicking on the section, you are redirected to a new page with 2 main sections:

General information

- Static text in English.
- A form to be filled and sent to INI's email address.

Innovation Hubs Contact Points

- Static text in English.
- Picture, name and contact details of the 7 innovation hubs Contact Points.

Nº 4. SCROLLING BANNERS:

- 5 scrolling banners with images linking to other sections:
 - NETWORK/What is Smart Farming?
 - NETWORK/Smart AKIS Network
 - NETWORK/EIP-AGRI and Thematic Networks.
 - Smart AKIS for Farmers.
 - Latest Smart-AKIS news

Nº 5. WHAT IS SMART FARMING?:

- Box with an image linking to the NETWORK/What is Smart Farming? section.

Nº 6. I AM A:

- Boxes or tiles with images and the names of agreed target groups. The name and number of target groups to be decided with BioSense and AUA. The following are proposed:
 - Farmers.
 - Agricultural advisors & extension services.
 - Researchers.
 - Providers of SFT solutions: industry and consultants.
 - Innovation Brokers???
- Static text in all languages. Text to be provided by INI and BioSense (Platform services).
- When clicking, you are redirected to a new page, where the benefits and services of the Network for such target groups are described, specifically pointing out through links the services provided by the Smart Farming Community Platform.

Nº 7. NEWS:

- Twitter Wall.
- The 3 latest news are displayed following tiles / blocks. When clicking on the news, a page opens with the piece of news.

Nº 8. SMART FARMING COMMUNITY PLATFORM:

- Buttons linking to the main functionalities or services of the platform. Hidden up until operational.

Nº 9. SMART AKIS PARTNERS:

- Logos of the partnership, linking to their websites.

Nº 10. OTHER INFORMATION:

- EU logo linked to EC website.
- Map: Map of contents to be provided by BioSense.
- Contact: Link to CONTACT section.
- Legal notice: To be provided by BioSense.
- Cookies Policy: To be provided by BioSense.
- Private area: Link to a private area for partners, if there is to be one.
- Links: A new page with links of interest. To be elaborated by INI following deliverables from WP3.1.

Nº 11. EIP-AGRI:

- EIP-AGRI logo and link.

4. Webportal content delivery

Distribution of contents delivery

Section/Area	Partner	Translation needed
NETWORK		
Smart AKIS	INI	Yes
What is Smart Farming?	AUA & INI	No
EIP-AGRI and Thematic Networks	INI	No
Partners following template	All partners	No
Innovation Hubs	INI	Yes
Results	WP Leaders	No
SMART FARMING PLATFORM		
Homepage	BioSense & INI	Yes
I AM A		
Target Groups information and services	INi & BioSense	Yes
OTHER INFORMATION		
Map of contents	BioSense	No
Legal notice	BioSense	No
Links	INI	

Work plan for contents delivery

Task	Partner	When
Agreement on webportal architecture	AUA & BioSense	20/05
Preliminary contents proposal	INI	25/05
Preliminary contents proposal – Partners	All	25/05
Review and agreement of texts by partners	All	01/06
Translation of texts to local languages	All partners	08/06
Upload of contents by developer	BioSense	10/06

smart **AKIS**
Smart Farming Thematic Network

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SMART AKIS PARTNERS:

DISSEMINATION WORK PLAN

Semester [Nº]

smart**AKIS**
Smart Farming Thematic Network

1. Expected Outputs

Expected Dissemination Outputs for this Semester are the following:

N°	Output	Target value	Responsible	Expected achievement time

2. Work Plan

The following activities are planned to be conducted during the semester, where the responsible partner is indicated:

ACTIVITY	WHO	WHEN
DISSEMINATION STRATEGY & PLAN		
DISSEMINATION TOOLS		
DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES		

3. Gantt Diagramme

WP5 DISSEMINATION			2016					
			March	April	May	June	July	Aug.
WP5	DISSEMINATION STRATEGY & PLAN	Partner						
			■			◆		
	DISSEMINATION TOOLS							
					◆			
	DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES							◆

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SMART AKIS PARTNERS:

DISSEMINATION REPORT

Semester [Nº]

Partner [Nº]

smart**AKIS**
Smart Farming Thematic Network

1. Summary of Dissemination Activities

Provide a summary on the following table of the activities carried out during the semester.

For each of the described activities you will have to provide some simple information in section 2, filling in proposed Fact Sheet. Please fill in a Factsheet for each activity and list in the summary table the reference to the fact Sheet supporting the reported activity.

Nº	Activity	Target value	Type	Sheet Nº
PUBLICITY MATERIALS				
1	Nº of publicity materials produced	1	Brochure	1
2	Nº of publicity materials distributed	50	Brochure	1
PUBLICATIONS				
1	Nº of popular publications and press releases on partners' media	2	News	2, 3 & 4
2	Nº of popular publications and press releases on specialised media.	1	Article	5
NETWORK EVENTS				
1	Nº of Network events held	1	Event	6
2	Nº of participants at Network events	60	Event	6
NON-NETWORK EVENTS				
1	Nº of events participated in	2	Event	7 & 8
2	Nº of participants at participated events	200	Event	7 & 8
NETWORKING & PERSON TO PERSON MEETINGS				
1	Nº of policy makers reached	0	Meeting	
2	Nº of Thematic Networks coordinated with	1	Meeting	10
3	Nº of Operational Groups and national EIP clusters coordinated with	4	Meeting	11, 12, 13 & 14

2. Fact sheets of reported dissemination activities

Fact Sheet Nº 1

Type of Activity	[e.g. press release communication / press article / press interview / TV-radio interview / event (pre)announcement / event organisation / conference / workshop / seminar / info day / bilateral meeting / trade fair / direct mailing / scientific publication / internet posts / social media posts / newsletter / promotional material distribution / person-to-person communication]
Date/Period of Activity	[DD/MM/YY or DD/MM/YY- DD/MM/YY]
Description	[e.g. published where/ title of article or event / place / date / recipients / organisers]
Coverage	[e.g. local / regional / national / European level]

Level	
Target Audience	[Describe briefly the type of audience]
Estimated Reach	[e.g. number of people the activity has reached / people that attended the event]
Support documents	[Internet link(s), press clipping, event programme, pictures, etc]

Fact Sheet № 2

Type of Activity	[e.g. press release communication / press article / press interview / tv-radio interview / event (pre)announcement / event organisation / conference / workshop / seminar / infoday / bilateral meeting / trade fair / direct mailing / scientific publication / internet posts / social media posts / newsletter / promotional material distribution / person-to-person communication]
Date/Period of Activity	[DD/MM/YY or DD/MM/YY- DD/MM/YY]
Description	[e.g. published where/ title of article or event / place / date / recipients / organisers]
Coverage Level	[e.g. local / regional / national / European level]
Target Audience	[Describe briefly the type of audience]
Estimated Reach	[e.g. number of people the activity has reached / people that attended the event]
Support documents	[Internet link(s), press clipping, event programme, pictures, etc]

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SMART AKIS PARTNERS:

REPUBLIC OF SERBIA
AUTONOMOUS PROVINCE OF VOJVODINA
PROVINCIAL SECRETARIAT FOR AGRICULTURE,
WATER MANAGEMENT AND FORESTRY

NETWORK DISSEMINATION REPORT Year [Nº]

smart**AKIS**
Smart Farming Thematic Network

1. Summary of Dissemination Activities

Provide a summary on the following table of the activities carried out during the semester.

For each of the described activities detailed information is provided in a Factsheet.

Nº	Activity	Partner	Date	Fact Sheet Nº

2. Fact Sheets of reported dissemination activities

Fact Sheet Nº 1

Type of Activity	[e.g. press release communication / press article / press interview / TV-radio interview / event (pre)announcement / event organisation / conference / workshop / seminar / info day / bilateral meeting / trade fair / direct mailing / scientific publication / internet posts / social media posts / newsletter / promotional material distribution / person-to-person communication]
Date/Period of Activity	[DD/MM/YY or DD/MM/YY- DD/MM/YY]
Description	[e.g. published where/ title of article or event / place / date / recipients / organisers]
Coverage Level	[e.g. local / regional / national / European level]
Target Audience	[Describe briefly the type of audience]
Estimated Reach	[e.g. number of people the activity has reached / people that attended the event]
Support documents	[Internet link(s), press clipping, event programme, pictures, etc]

3. Dissemination balanced scorecard

INDICATOR	CATEGORY	TARGET VALUE	PERIOD VALUE	AGGREG. VALUE	ACHIEVEMENT %
DISSEMINATION STRATEGY & PLAN					
Dissemination Plan	Output	1			
Nº of meetings of Dissemination Work Group	Output	5			
Nº of Dissemination Work Plans	Output	5			
Nº of six-monthly Dissemination Reports	Output	5			
Nº of annual Dissemination Reports	Output	3			
Nº of Dissemination Updates distributed	Output	30			
DISSEMINATION TOOLS					
Nº of webportal	Output	1			
Nº of social media accounts	Output	3			
Nº of publicity materials	Output	4			
Nº of digital newsletters distributed	Output	3			
Nº of webportal visitors	Result	2.000			
Nº of webportal pages visited	Result	10.000			
Nº of Twitter followers	Result	1.000			
Nº of Facebook page likes	Result	500			
Nº of Facebook page visits	Result	100			
Nº of people outreached by Facebook page	Result	1.000			
Nº of people outreached by digital newsletter	Result	3.000			
Nº of people outreached with publicity materials	Result	2.500			
Nº of stakeholders from Innovation Hubs registered on the Platform	Result	700			
Nº of stakeholders from other EU countries registered on the Platform	Result	2.500			
Nº of visits to Smart Farming Community Platform	Result	2.000			
DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES					
Nº of regional Innovation Workshops held	Output	21			
Nº of open transnational Innovation Workshops held	Output	1			
Nº of Network Final Conference held	Output	1			
Nº of non-network events where Network has been disseminated	Output	50			
Nº of popular articles published in partners' media	Output	50			
Nº of popular articles published in specialised media	Output	30			
Nº of press releases issued	Output	20			
Nº of participants on regional Innovation Workshops	Result	700			
Nº of participants on transnational Innovation Workshop	Result	60			
Nº of participants on Final Conference	Result	60			
Nº of people outreached at non-network events	Result	1.250			
Nº of policy makers reached with recommendations and policy briefs	Result	100			
Nº of Thematic Networks coordinated with	Result	8			
Nº of Operational Groups and national EIP clusters coordinated with	Result	50			

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Smart Farming Thematic Network

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SMART AKIS PARTNERS:

Smart AKIS
Dissemination Balanced Scorecard

INDICATOR	CATEGORY OF INDICATOR	METHOD OF CALCULATION	VERIFICATION MEANS	OWNER	PERIODICITY	ACHIEVEMENT TIME	TARGET VALUE
DISSEMINATION STRATEGY & PLAN							
Dissemination Plan	Output	Deliverable	Document	INI	Once	M6	1
Nº of meetings of Dissemination Work Group	Output	Nº of Skype meetinhs helds	Email minutes	INI	Six-monthly	M30	5
Nº of Dissemination Work Plans	Output	Document agreed by Dissemination Work Group	Document	INI	Six-monthly	M30	5
Nº of six-monthly Dissemination Reports	Output	Document agreed by Dissemination Work Group	Document	INI	Six-monthly	M30	5
Nº of annual Dissemination Reports	Output	Deliverable	Report	INI	Yearly	M15, M24, M30	3
Nº of Dissemination Updates distributed	Output	Nº of subsequent Dissemination Update email	Email	INI	Six-monthly	M30	30
DISSEMINATION TOOLS							
Nº of webportal	Output	Webportal	Operational webportal	INI	Once	M6	1
Nº of social media accounts	Output	Facebook, Twitter & Youtube	Regularly updated accounts	INI	Once	M6	3
Nº of publicity materials	Output	Leaflet, brochure, roll-up and bookmark	Materials	INI	Once	M6	4
Nº of digital newsletters distributed	Output	Nº of newsletters elaborated and distributed	Mailchimp Email	INI	Yearly	M30	3
Nº of webportal visitors	Result	Nº of visitors a month	Google Analytics	INI	Monthly	M30	1.000
Nº of webportal pages visited	Result	Nº of pages visited a month	Google Analytics	INI	Monthly	M31	2.000
Nº of Twitter followers	Result	Nº of aggregated followers	Twitter profile	INI	Monthly	M32	1.000
Nº of Facebook page likes	Result	Nº of aggregated Likes to Page & Posts	Facebook page statistics	INI	Monthly	M33	500
Nº of Facebook page visits	Result	Nº of visits to page a month	Facebook page statistics	INI	Monthly	M34	100
Nº of people outreached by Facebook page	Result	Nº of people outreached a month	Facebook page statistics	INI	Monthly	M35	1.000
Nº of people outreached by digital newsletter	Result	Addition of the number of recipients of the 3 numbers of the digital newsletter	Mailchimp Distribution List	INI	February & December 2017, May 2017	M36	3.000

Smart AKIS
Dissemination Balanced Scorecard

INDICATOR	CATEGORY OF INDICATOR	METHOD OF CALCULATION	VERIFICATION MEANS	OWNER	PERIODICITY	ACHIEVEMENT TIME	TARGET VALUE
Nº of people outreached with publicity materials	Result	Nº of copies of promotional materials (leaflet & brochure) distributed in paper and digitally	Partners' Dissemination Activity Report	All partners	Six-monthly	M37	2.500
Nº of stakeholders from Innovation Hubs registered on the Platform	Result	Nº of registered users	Platform's administration system	Biosense	Six-monthly	M30	700
Nº of stakeholders from other EU countries registered on the Platform	Result	Nº of registered users	Platform's administration system	Biosense	Six-monthly	M30	2.500
Nº of visits to Smart Farming Community Platform	Result	Nº of monthly visits	Platform's administration system	Biosense	Six-monthly	M30	2.000
DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES							
Nº of regional Innovation Workshops held	Output	Nº of workshops held	Programme, attendance list, pics, press clippings	All partners	Yearly	M30	21
Nº of open transnational Innovation Workshops held	Output	Nº of workshops held	Programme, attendance list, pics, press clippings	BioSense	2.018	M30	1
Nº of Network Final Conference held	Output	Nº of conferences held	Programme, attendance list, pics, press clippings	INI & AUA	2.018	M30	1
Nº of non-network events where Network has been disseminated	Output	Nº of events where partners have actively disseminated the Network: distribution of materials, stand or a presentation	Partners' Dissemination Activity Report	All partners	Six-monthly	M30	50
Nº of popular articles published in partners' media	Output	Press clipping of article by Partner on relation to the Network	Partners' Dissemination Activity Report	All partners	Six-monthly	M30	50
Nº of popular articles published in specialised media	Output	Press clipping of article by Network or Partner on relation to the Network	Partners' Dissemination Activity Report	All partners	Six-monthly	M30	30
Nº of press releases issued	Output	Nº of press releases in English and local languages issued	Partners' Dissemination Activity Report	All partners	Six-monthly	M31	20
Nº of participants on regional Innovation Workshops	Result	Nº of attendants	Registration List	Innovation Hubs Partners	End of 2017 & 2017	End of 2017 & 2018	700
Nº of participants on transnational Innovation Workshop	Result	Nº of attendants	Registration List	INI	August 2018	August 2018	60
Nº of participants on Final Conference	Result	Nº of attendants	Registration List	INI	August 2018	August 2018	60
Nº of people outreached at non-network events	Result	Nº of attendants on events where partners have actively disseminated the Network	Partners' Dissemination Activity Report	All partners	Six-monthly	Six-monthly	1.250
Nº of policy makers reached with recommendations and policy briefs	Result	Nº of people reached: combination of bilateral meetings + attendance to workshops and dissemination events	Partners' Dissemination Activity Report	All partners	Six-monthly	Six-monthly	100
Nº of Thematic Networks coordinated with	Result	Nº of TNs informed on Network activities and events	Partners' Dissemination Activity Report	INI	Six-monthly	Six-monthly	8
Nº of Operational Groups and national EIP clusters coordinated with	Result	Nº of OGs informed on Network activities and events	Partners' Dissemination Activity Report	All partners	Six-monthly	Six-monthly	50